

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D9.6

Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities Report and Plan

March 2023

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
RMC-C&E	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UoE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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Contents

List of Figures	10
List of Tables	11
List of Abbreviations	12
1 INTRODUCTION	16
2 PURPOSE OF THE PLAN	17
2.1 The two pillars of promotion: Communication, Dissemination	17
2.1.1 Communication.....	17
2.1.2 Dissemination	17
2.1.3 Targets of the C&D Strategy.....	18
2.2 exploitation purpose and deliverables.....	18
2.2.1 exploitation.....	18
2.2.2 structure of the deliverable	19
3 AUDIENCES TO REACH	20
3.1 Choice Of Listings.....	20
4 PROMOTIONAL CHANNELS & MEANS	21
4.1 Potential Promotional Channels.....	21
4.1.1 The MES-CoBraD Website	21
4.1.2 Social Media.....	21
4.1.3 Blogs and News Websites	22
4.1.4 Journals	23
4.1.5 Online Collaboration Platforms.....	24
4.1.6 Publishing Platforms.....	24
4.1.7 Data Repositories- Databases	25
4.1.8 Partners' websites/blogs	26
4.1.9 Partners' Journals.....	26
4.1.10 Partners' events	27
4.1.11 External events	27
4.2 Synergies	28
4.3 Horizon Result Booster	28
4.4 Promotional Means.....	28
4.4.1 Logo	28
4.4.2 Leaflet.....	28
4.4.3 Poster	28
4.4.4 MES-CoBraD Presentation	29

4.4.5	Articles	29
4.4.6	Reports	29
4.4.7	Working Documents	29
4.4.8	Scientific Publications	29
4.4.9	Newsletters & Electronic promotion	29
5	REPORT ON C&D ACTIVITIES.....	31
5.1	Website	31
5.1.1	Website Content sample	32
5.1.2	Zenodo and OpenAire repositories	32
5.2	Social Media	33
5.2.1	MES-CoBraD Twitter	33
5.2.2	MES-CoBraD Facebook	34
5.2.3	MES-CoBraD LinkedIn	35
5.3	Partners' websites.....	35
5.4	MES-CoBraD Newsletters & Videos	36
5.4.1	MES-CoBraD Newsletters.....	36
5.4.2	Partners' Newsletters	39
5.4.3	MES-CoBraD Videos.....	40
5.5	Promotional Materials developed	40
5.6	Publications	40
5.7	Organization of Events.....	41
5.7.1	Kick-Off Meeting, 12-13 April 2021, Athens, Greece.....	41
5.7.2	MES for the CoBraD Workshop.....	41
5.7.3	1 st Project Meeting - Workshop.....	41
5.7.4	BMC Workshop	41
5.7.5	MES-CoBraD poster in Liber conference.....	41
5.7.6	MES-CoBraD Joint Projects' Webinar	41
5.7.7	MES-CoBraD at the "Days of Neurology 2022" conference	41
5.7.8	2 nd , 3 rd , 4 th Project meeting.....	41
5.7.9	CDE Planning workshop	42
5.7.10	Other events	42
6	EXPLOITATION OUTCOMES.....	43
6.1	MES-CoBraD Platform.....	43
6.1.1	Description	43
6.1.2	Exploitation Goals	44

6.2	MES-CoBraD Pilot Use Cases	45
6.2.1	Description of the Pilots	45
6.3	Policy Recommendations	46
6.3.1	Description	46
6.3.2	Exploitation Goals	46
6.4	Scientific & Technical Knowledge	46
6.4.1	Description	46
7	MES-COBRA D BUSINESS CASES FOR EXPLOITATION	48
7.1	Introduction	48
7.2	Plan For Exploiting The MES-CoBraD Platform.....	48
7.2.1	Business model exploration	48
7.2.2	Business Model experimentation	48
7.2.3	MES-CoBraD Business Model implementation.....	55
7.3	Plan For Exploiting The MES-CoBraD Components.....	57
8	SUSTAINABILITY PLAN.....	58
8.1	Context.....	58
8.2	Methodology	59
9	PARTNERS' INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION PLANS	61
9.1	Consortium members' exploitation plans	61
9.1.1	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)	61
9.1.2	Neurological Institute of Athens (NIA)	61
9.1.3	Fundació privada institut de recerca de l'hospital de la santa creu i sant pau (SP)	62
9.1.4	Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB-LSTS)	62
9.1.5	Uppsala University (UU)	62
9.1.6	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center (CHS-RMC)	62
9.1.7	King's College London (KCL)	63
9.1.8	Holistic.....	63
9.1.9	Software Imagination & Vision (SIMAVI)	63
9.1.10	LIBER.....	64
9.1.11	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A. (ENG)	64
9.1.12	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P. - TRADE NAME: EVOLUTION PROJECTS(EVOL)	64
9.1.13	University of Edinburgh (UE)	65
9.1.14	CyberEthics Lab. (CEL)	65
10	MONITORING AND IMPACT.....	66
10.1	Analysis Tools	66

10.1.1	Website Analytics.....	66
10.1.2	Social Media Platforms Embedded Analytics	66
10.2	Monitoring Table	66
11	Next Steps / Conclusions.....	68
11.1	Actions on CDE online channels.....	68
11.1.1	Website	68
11.1.2	Social Media	68
11.1.3	Online Media.....	68
11.1.4	Partner’s Website / Blogs	68
11.2	Update on Materials & New content.....	68
11.2.1	Materials update	68
11.2.2	Infographics	68
11.2.3	Videos.....	69
11.3	Events’ participation	69
11.3.1	Workshops, Public Events, Demonstrations & Material	69
11.3.2	Conferences.....	69
11.4	Exploitation & Business-Related actions.....	69
11.4.1	Market analysis	69
11.4.2	Value propositions – targeted business model(s).....	69
11.5	C&D&E plan and report update.....	69

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Website Traffic analysis.....	31
Figure 2: Website users / lifetime	31
Figure 3: Website traffic origin per communication channel.....	31
Figure 4: Website traffic per country of origin	32
Figure 5: Website post on partner’s participation in conference in 2022.....	32
Figure 6: Twitter impressions from June 2021 up to September 2021	33
Figure 7: Twitter impressions from October 2021 up to December 2021.....	33
Figure 8: Twitter impressions from January 2022 up to March 2022.....	34
Figure 9: Twitter Impressions from April 2022 up to March 2023	34
Figure 10: Facebook page Reach – lifetime.....	34
Figure 11: Facebook page visits lifetime	34
Figure 12: Facebook page new likes rate – lifetime	35
Figure 13: Indicative LinkedIn page visits chart for the last 12 months up to March 2023.....	35
Figure 14: MES-CoBraD Newsletter December 2021 – Sample.....	37
Figure 15: MES-CoBraD Newsletter May 2022 – Sample	38
Figure 16: MES-CoBraD November 2022 – Sample.....	39
Figure 17: RMC-C&E Newsletter – Sample.....	40
Figure 18: MES-CoBraD platform architecture	44
Figure 19: MES-CoBraD workshop sample picture of platform used for the BMC drafting.....	49
Figure 20: CDE Interactive Workshop, Customer Segments Question	51
Figure 21: CDE Interactive Workshop, Value Propositions Question	51
Figure 22: CDE Interactive Workshop, Key Activities Question	52
Figure 23: CDE Interactive Workshop, Key Partners Question.....	52
Figure 24: CDE Interactive Workshop, Key Resources Question	53
Figure 25: CDE Interactive Workshop, C&D Channels Question	53
Figure 26: MES-CoBraD BMC (v2).....	56
Figure 27: MES-CoBraD CDE Strategy.....	59
Figure 28: CDE Monitoring template samples.....	66

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Targets for each monitored C&D activity	18
Table 2 Aim & purpose per social media channel.....	22
Table 3: MES-CoBraD Newsletter 1 statistics.....	37
Table 4: MES-CoBraD Newsletter 2 statistics.....	38
Table 5: MES-CoBraD Newsletter 3 statistics.....	39
Table 6: Exploitation objectives for the MES-CoBraD platform	44
Table 7: MES-CoBraD pilot activities.....	45
Table 8: Exploitation objectives for MES-CoBraD policy recommendations.....	46
Table 9: Exploitation objectives for the MES-CoBraD scientific, technical and educational knowledge ..	47
Table 10: Exploitable Items related to the MES-CoBraD research framework and data infrastructure solution along with the main stakeholders.....	58

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
DoA	Description of Action
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
EB	Ethics Board
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
H2020	Horizon 2020
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
Mx	Month x
No.	Number
PC	Project Coordinator
TBD	To Be Decided
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable will serve as the update on the D9.1 Communication and Dissemination plan of the project, including the targeted audiences, promotional channels and means, for consortium partners (experts and non-experts) to engage, by actively contributing to the communication and dissemination of the project's outputs.

Being a public document, it can also be used by external stakeholder groups as information sheet on the Communication and Dissemination plan of the MES-CoBraD project.

3. Short summary of results

This report mainly outlines the strategy and tools that will be used to implement the MES-CoBraD Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan. The major activities and tools used for communicating and disseminating the project's results will be explained, alongside with the responsibilities of the consortium and timeline, where possible. It entails how to share the MES-CoBraD scope and results with the appropriate audiences. In doing so, it defines the communication, dissemination and promotional channels and means that will be used for this distribution and reports on all the above-mentioned activities.

In particular, the promotional means to be used include but are not limited to the MES-CoBraD logo and standard dissemination tools, such as those comprising the visual identity of the project. Specialised articles, reports, scientific publications, infographics, videos, and presentations tailor made to support specific project needs, will be a core aspect of the project's Communication and Dissemination strategy as well.

The implemented promotional activities include the management of social media channels for promoting the project scope and activities, the publication of articles in partners' websites, and the design of MES-CoBraD website and promotional material along with specialised material and Communication Dissemination & Exploitation (CDE) actions to promote specific events and support the partners participating.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan will be formally updated in Month 36 in order to analyse and assess the implemented use of the promotion channels and means and carry out updates/adjustments of the strategy where necessary. It was updated and aligned with the project's Stakeholder's engagement strategy delivered in M7.

4. Evidence of Accomplishment

This report serves as evidence of accomplishment for the above-described actions.

Executive Summary

The main objective of MES-CoBraD (Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders) is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in the Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependences through Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols, in light of the MES-CoBraD Agreement and associated challenges.

Towards this notion, MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.

The application of the assessment framework will be implemented through the MES-CoBraD Platform. This platform aims at addressing all the challenges (clinical, research and technological). MES-CoBraD aims integrating solutions that enable individual researchers to maximise impact through collaborative value creation and Open Science practices, including secure data sharing, and sharing of global expertise that is otherwise unavailable in a single institution. The platform will also provide a module (MES-CoBraD Expert System) which aims at improving personalized medicine approaches in real-world practice by including ML and AI in data analysis.

This report mainly outlines the strategy and tools that are used so far and will be used to implement the MES-CoBraD Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (C&D&E) Plan.

As far as the (C&D) plan, the major activities to be undertaken and tools to be used for communicating and disseminating the project's results will be explained, alongside with the responsibilities of the consortium and timeline, where possible. It entails how to share the MES-CoBraD scope and results with the appropriate audiences (section 3). In doing so, it defines the communication, dissemination and promotional channels and means, as described in section 4, which will be used for this distribution. The plan concludes by enlisting the implemented promotional activities so far, presented in section 5. These include the establishment of social media channels for promoting the project scope and activities, the publication of articles in partners' websites, and the design of MES-CoBraD website and promotional material. Regarding the present Exploitation Plan, this report presents the exploitation plan that the entire consortium of the MES-CoBraD project implements during the project lifetime, to sustain the, described in section 6, outcomes beyond the end of the project, and the sustainability plan, which is described in section 8, that paves the way for MES-CoBraD vision to maximise its expected impact. The MES-CoBraD solution and platform are the main project outcomes, and the Business plan is developed for its future commercialisation by the partners who are interested in (section 7). This is the second revision of the 'Business and Exploitation Plan,' (based on the 'D9.5 Business and Exploitation Plan V-1')

The MES-CoBraD outcomes will be exploited by the different partner organisations, in Health provision Organisations, on patients (end-users) and in Academia. Each organisation will exploit different outcomes because of their different nature. With regard to exploitation plan of the MES-CoBraD platform by stakeholders, the results of the project will inform health authorities more accurately of the healthcare needs of people with CoBraD diseases, their social barriers to healthcare access and compliance, as well as the real-world efficiency and safety of approved therapies. The exploitation of the MES-CoBraD platform can serve as a plan for developing comprehensive RWD registries for Clinical Trials beyond CoBraD and allow more accurate real-time assessments of health population authorities.

The (C&D&E) Plan will be further updated in the final report D9.7 "Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities Report and Plan", which will be finalised in Month 36 (March 2024), to analyse and assess the implemented promotional and exploitation activities and carry out updates or adjustments of

the whole strategy where needed.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) project aims at improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in the Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependences through Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols.

Experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, advocacy and marketing & communication across Europe, couple clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and precision analytics focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.

The MES-CoBraD upcoming platform will be the next step the project will take towards applying the assessment framework developed, addressing all present challenges (clinical, research and technological). The secure data sharing provided by the integrated platform will further enable involved scientists in maximising their research impact and expertise sharing, reaching the global community. Furthermore, the MES-CoBraD Expert System module provided by the platform aims to improve personalized medicine approaches in real-world practice.

The project aims to include in its processes stakeholders across the spectrum of interested actors. These stakeholders are both external and internal, as major groups are also represented by project partners. However, it is acknowledged that the two key groups of MES-CoBraD stakeholders and potential users of the MES-CoBraD Platform, are scientists in the health and social health fields as well as stakeholders working in engineering and computer science at a national, regional and global level. Other groups that should be actively engaged are scientists in general, trade unions, industry associations, business networks, NGOs, and the civil society and general public.

Communication and Dissemination Plan

Consequently, it is of vital importance that information regarding the project and its outcomes to be disseminated at an early stage, so that all these groups become aware of and then involved in the project's activities early on, so they actively participate in the design of the MES-CoBraD Platform and the co-creation of the scientific processes and results. The Communication and Dissemination Plan aligns with the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (D3.6), a KPI-driven strategic document that will ensure fostering community engagement and maximizing impact.

Given the above, the main purpose of this (C&D) plan/report is the development of an effective strategy for the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) of information and results of the MES-CoBraD project to the relevant audiences, in addition to the reporting of the so far (C&D) implemented activities. The C&D strategy addresses the What (creation and planning of the CD activities)-to Whom (identification of the targeted audiences)- and How elements (analysis of potential promotional channels).

Exploitation Plan

Additionally, the aforementioned potential outcomes are crucial to be adequately exploited to ensure the sustainability and maximisation of their expected impact. Towards this notion, this Exploitation report includes the updated version of 'D9.5 Business and Exploitation Plan V-1', combined with reporting the already implemented steps.

2 PURPOSE OF THE PLAN

Communication and Dissemination Plan

The CDE Plan is a periodic report elaborating on the exact ways in which the consortium of the MES-CoBraD project can increase its outreach and disseminate the project's results to the relevant audiences. It outlines the strategy and tools that will be employed to implement said strategy. The major activities to be undertaken and tools to be used for communicating and disseminating the project's results will be explained, alongside with the responsibilities of the consortium and timeline, where possible.

This report entails how to share the MES-CoBraD scope and results with the appropriate audiences. In doing so, it defines the communication, dissemination and promotional channels and means that will be employed. It will follow relevant research and novelties in the fields of health and social health as well in computer science and engineering that will help in the modelling process and in achieving the project results. The document lists the different channels needed to reach several relevant target groups, through their preferred communication methods, e.g., a social media pack, relevant conferences, identification of relevant media channels and synergies that could be created with other EU projects or networks. This report also includes the monitoring templates set for events, media work and any other dissemination activity undertaken by the partners. This deliverable will be further updated in Month 36. However, the project's co-creation/co-design approach implies that the CDE plan has far more than the usual C&D dynamics paired with exploitation actions, mostly triggered by the evolving stakeholders that will be engaged and the development and operation of the MES-CoBraD Platform. Consequently, a cross-cutting, uniform, and transparent C&D approach will be established with continuous improvements/adjustments.

This exploitation report/plan included is the updated version of the deliverable D 9.5 "Business and Exploitation plan"¹ that will be revised annually and presents the planning and simultaneously the reporting of the project's exploitation and sustainability.

2.1 THE TWO PILLARS OF PROMOTION: COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION

Before entering the full length of the report, we provide the basic definitions of communication and dissemination to better understand their significance and their respective role in shaping a solid strategy leading on the exploitation of this project.

2.1.1 COMMUNICATION

Communication is the process of informing the widest possible audience, including the media and the public, regarding the project and its results. Its main objective is to reach out to any interested parties and the society and show the impact that MES-CoBraD can achieve. The main audiences targeted for communication purposes are the general public, patients, social health scientists, and civil society.

2.1.2 DISSEMINATION

Dissemination is the process of transferring produced knowledge and results in order to enable others to use and exploit them. Dissemination focuses on the results and outcomes of the initiative, rather than the initiative itself, as well as the ways in which they can be exploited by interested parties. Main audiences suitable for dissemination are the ones who have the ability to use the results in their operation. In the case of MES-CoBraD these are health scientists, doctors, engineers, computer scientists and patients themselves.

¹ [D9.5 on Zenodo](#)

2.1.3 TARGETS OF THE C&D STRATEGY

In order to be certain that the results of MES-CoBraD will be communicated and disseminated several targets for most of the C&D activities have been set. The progress towards these targets will be monitored on a regular basis so as to confirm that the project is on track to achieve them or takes the appropriate measures if needed.

The following table presents the targets for each monitored C&D activity. The ways to achieve these targets are described in the document at hand.

Table 1 Targets for each monitored C&D activity

Activity	Target	Means of verification
Development and maintenance of the project website	The project website will spread the objectives and results as widely as possible.	At least 5000 visitors will have accessed the website by the end of the project.
Production of project documentation and printing materials	The project brochure will be a key document, to be disseminated by the Consortium as a whole and by each Consortium partner, as widely as possible.	500 copies of the project brochure will be distributed throughout the project duration. Due to Covid 19 pandemic the project documentation will be also distributed electronically.
Organisation of presentation / feedback sessions (1 per year at major forums or trade shows, relevant to the project theme)	Key stakeholders from Europe and beyond will be invited to presentation/ feedback sessions, to provide the project with their inputs (visions and alternative solutions).	An attendance of 40-70 delegates per event. Due to Covid 19 pandemic online presence will be considered as well.

2.2 EXPLOITATION PURPOSE AND DELIVERABLES

2.2.1 EXPLOITATION

Exploitation can solely start once the research/platform results are available. It focuses on concretely using research results for commercial, societal, and political purposes. Depending on the nature and scope of this project, a broad spectrum of results may be recognised as exploitable. In this context, this report aims to:

- › Involve in setting up the environment for commercialising the MES-CoBraD solution and further exploit the outcomes.
- › Identify all the potential exploitable assets of the project, along with the results to be sustained following the end of the project.
- › Specify a plan for exploiting each one of the various assets, including exploitation of the asset by individual partners (where applicable) and joint exploitation.
- › Elaborate the plan including identification of the target market(s), identification of interested customers and stakeholders, market analysis, as well as exploitation modalities.
- › Report the so far implemented exploitation activities and actions taken and the next steps.

Finally, the key outcome of the project, the MES-CoBraD platform and its individual components will be

implemented and deployed in pilot conditions. Therefore, the upcoming versions of this report will focus on the elaboration of the business model and the business plan to improve the commercialization of the project.

2.2.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The first section of the present exploitation report introduces the content and the overall scope. The second section presents the overall exploitation plan and the project outcomes with their basic characteristics. The third section defines the business cases for the different target groups and the approach of the business model that the consortium members will develop. The fourth section presents the sustainability plan and the specific methodology that will take place during the project life cycle. And finally, the fifth section describes the possible next steps of the project's exploitation.

3 AUDIENCES TO REACH

3.1 CHOICE OF LISTINGS

An understanding of stakeholders' interests, drivers and barriers is essential for effective communication and the prioritisation of tools for communication. Understanding stakeholder motivations will enable the consortium to effectively engage, communicate with, and promote current and future dialogue between different stakeholders. However, whilst communication activities will be tailored for different stakeholder groups, the core scientific content will remain consistent—under no circumstances will the scientific findings of the project be played down, regardless of the interests of certain stakeholder groups.

One of the main goals of the MES-CoBraD C&D Plan is to be used as a feedback mechanism that will enable stakeholders outside the consortium to provide their knowledge to the project and to co-create the MES-CoBraD platform. This will also take place within the scope of WP3 where the relevant stakeholders will be mapped and analysed so they can contribute to the project development through direct engagement activities. It is essential that feedback and suggestions is collected from a variety of individuals with complementary skills and backgrounds, in order to increase the robustness of the project's results.

The target audiences of MES-CoBraD on its initial deployment phase consists of the following groups.

- › TG1: Researchers
- › TG2: Research Producing Organisations (RPOs)
- › TG3: Research funders
- › TG4: Research libraries
- › TG5: Industry
- › TG6: Policy Makers, including public sector entities
- › TG7: Citizen Scientists
- › TG8: Research infrastructures and e-infrastructures
- › TG9: Health Providers, both public and private
- › TG10: Patients, patients advocates
- › TG11: General public

4 PROMOTIONAL CHANNELS & MEANS

In order to deliver the project's messaging to the targeted audiences, the appropriate channels and means have been developed and maintained. The promotional channels are the ways, or routes, through which the messages may find the desired destinations, i.e., articles in the MES-CoBraD website, posts on social media, the presentation of the project's results in conferences, the participation in events, etc. A promotional means is the medium that encapsulates the promoted message and is distributed via the channels, i.e., a publication, an infographic, a video, etc.

Each combination of promotional channel and means is unique and serves a different purpose and level of promotion. For example, a scientific publication or a working document is a report with more technical details, aiming to give scientists and researchers a more thorough aspect of an outcome of the action. On the other hand, an infographic is more suitable to feature the fundamentals of the action and its results for a broader audience, while a policy brief is expected to target policymakers.

4.1 POTENTIAL PROMOTIONAL CHANNELS

4.1.1 THE MES-COBRA D WEBSITE

The MES-CoBraD Website (<http://www.mes-cobrad.eu/>) serves as a one-stop shop and is the centre of the promotional process. It is used for both pillars of promotion and contains (or is linked to) every promotional material of the action. The website's development has been completed in May 2021 and consists of several informational webpages, mainly information about the action (concept, objectives and work structure) as well as pages showcasing specific activities (e.g., the organisation of events), or major outcomes, namely reports, publications, infographics, etc. A detailed description of the website and its components is presented in "D9.2 Website"² issued in July 2021. The website also promotes transparency of the project's scientific capabilities and processes, assumptions and results, by providing background information and a direct link to the MES-CoBraD Platform. It is worth mentioning that the MES-CoBraD is in its final stages of development and will be soon accessible through the website. More on the creation of the MES-CoBraD platform will be available in the upcoming report, "D.7.2 MES-CoBraD platform Release 1.00". The website uses responsive web-design enabling access from different screen sizes/platforms of desktops and smartphones.

In order to increase the visibility and traffic to the website, as well as the number of downloads of the reports a continuous campaign is active via the other communication and dissemination channels (i.e., social media, blog articles, communication lists, etc.), as well as relying on cross-promotion on behalf of the partners, through their own channels and platforms. Moreover, several opinion blog articles containing relevant keywords will be posted on the website in order to boost search engine optimisation and achieve showcase of the website in the top search lists of search engine results for relevant queries.

4.1.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media provide an online platform for everyone who has internet access to exchange opinions, knowledge, and expertise. Thus, it is a very effective medium for organisations to implement marketing and promotional campaigns. In MES-CoBraD, social media are used in order to promote the action and its results to every possible stakeholder, not only for communication purposes but also for dissemination and exploitation reasons. Social Media presence and activity is also very well suited to indirect promotion and dissemination activities, as linked subjects that are being discussed/shared could allow for the introduction of the MES-CoBraD project in general and its relevant, specific messages in particular. This is of key importance especially at the initial stages of the project, when an initial "follower club" should

² [D9.2 on Zenodo](#)

be established.

The following table presents the aim and reason for the three key social media channels.

Table 2 Aim & purpose per social media channel

Social Media Channel	Purpose	Plan
Twitter	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the scientific community, the health department community and the civil society.	At least 1 weekly update on current affairs and project's progress.
LinkedIn	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the scientific and policymaking community.	At least 1 monthly update Ad hoc posts on project's progress.
Facebook	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the society	At least 1 weekly update on current affairs.
YouTube	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the scientific community, the health department community and the civil society	At least 1-3 videos will be developed in the project lifetime

Twitter

Twitter³ is an online social networking service on which users post and interact with short messages (less than 280 characters). It is ideal for short announcements of the action's outcomes and will be used ad hoc. Via its account in Twitter MES-CoBraD is envisaged to reach a wide variety of audiences suitable primarily for communication and dissemination purposes.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn⁴ is a business and employment-oriented social network allowing individuals and organisations to promote their professional progress and outcomes. The MES-CoBraD page in LinkedIn will be used to target more specialised audiences within the framework of dissemination and exploitation and will be updated at least once in a month.

Facebook

Facebook⁵ is a social networking app for sharing photos and videos with other user and it is ideal for communicating with members of the general public. Via its channel MES-CoBraD will post pictures on health issues which are relevant to the brain disorders issues and will communicate its scope and objective to the wider public.

YouTube

YouTube will be used in order to host and promote the MES-CoBraD videos, which would be of wide variety, such as interviews, explanatory videos, etc. The MES-CoBraD YouTube channel will be created as soon as the 1st video is created.

4.1.3 BLOGS AND NEWS WEBSITES

In the following sections, a list of high-calibre media websites, through which it would be beneficial for MES-CoBraD to be communicated, is presented. These websites often feature opinion articles from

³ <https://twitter.com/MESCoBraD>

⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/in/mes-cobrad-4b445a212/>

⁵ <https://www.facebook.com/mescobrad/>

external sources in their “Opinion” columns, so it is possible to include an article regarding MES-CoBraD as well. However, it is worth mentioning that this is an indicative, non-exhaustive list which may be modified if it is considered necessary.

EC website (CORDIS)

MES-CoBraD will be in close co-operation with the departments of the European commission and will update the cordis webpage⁶ with its progress.

EC Success Stories Webpage

It is envisaged that MES-CoBraD will publish a couple of articles featuring its outcomes via the EC Success Stories webpage⁷. These articles are expected to increase the participation of experts in the stakeholder groups.

Neuroscience News

Neuroscience News⁸ is a website focused on neuroscience and MES-CoBraD may share the projects research development and disseminate results and news.

Association of Alternative News media

AAN⁹ aims to strengthen alternative journalism through advocacy and education. This platform could provide an opportunity for MES-CoBraD to further communicate its goals and results.

Neurology Today

Neurology Today¹⁰ is the official news source of the American Academy of Neurology and MES-CoBraD partners could expand the project’s reach by publishing.

BMC Public Health

BMC Public Health¹¹ is an open access, peer-reviewed journal that considers articles on the epidemiology of disease and the understanding of all aspects of public health. During the projects lifecycle the possibility to publish on BMC may be investigated.

JAMA Network

Jama Network¹² with a vast assembly of Medical Journals and a specific one for neurology (JAMA Neurology) may provide another platform for MES-CoBraD’s CD targets.

4.1.4 JOURNALS

Research*eu

Research*eu Results magazine¹³ covers topics of research interest in the EU. Through this channel, outcomes of MES-CoBraD will be communicated and disseminated to scientists, policymakers in the EU and Member States (MS), and the general public.

Science, Technology, & Human Values

For more than forty years Science, Technology, & Human Values¹⁴ has provided the forum for cutting-

⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/965422>

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/success-stories>

⁸ <https://neurosciencenews.com/>

⁹ <https://aan.org/>

¹⁰ <https://journals.lww.com/neurotodayonline/pages/default.aspx>

¹¹ <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/>

¹² <https://jamanetwork.com/>

¹³ https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/home_en.html

¹⁴ <http://journals.sagepub.com/home/sth>

edge research and debate in the field of science and technology studies. ST&HV is a double-blind peer-reviewed, bi-monthly, international, interdisciplinary journal containing research, analyses and commentary on the development and dynamics of science and technology, including their relationship to politics, society, and culture. The journal publishes work from scholars in a diverse range of disciplines across the social sciences.

Ethics and Information Technology

The journal¹⁵ is a peer-reviewed journal dedicated to advancing the dialogue between moral philosophy and the field of information and communication technology (ICT). The journal aims to foster and promote reflection and analysis which is intended to make a constructive contribution to answering the ethical, social, and political questions associated with the adoption, use, and development of ICT.

4.1.5 ONLINE COLLABORATION PLATFORMS

Capacity4Dev

Capacity4Dev is the European Commission's knowledge sharing platform for development cooperation aiming to improve capacity building. This is done among others by enabling cross-learning between practitioners from EU institutions and other organisations. The platform has over 25,000 members who share, learn, and collaborate on the fields of sustainable development. This channel is ideal for dissemination and exploitation purposes since its members are scientists, industrialists, EU staff, and sustainable development professionals from EU MS, policymakers at EU & global level, as well as civil societies.

AI4EU

Artificial Intelligence for Europe¹⁶ is the first European Artificial Intelligence On-Demand Platform and Ecosystem with the support of the European Commission under the H2020 programme. AI4EU is a large European ecosystem spanning the 28 countries to facilitate collaboration between all Europeans actors in AI. MES-CoBraD may demonstrate the capabilities of the platform to be developed and further communicate the project goals and research results.

European Academy of Neurology

EAN¹⁷ is a non-profit, independent organization that aims to promote quality in neurology and bring together Europe's best clinicians, educators and scientists in the field to foster and support the development of neurological excellence in Europe and across the world. MES-CoBraD with its unique approach on improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes on people with CoBraD may approach EAN in an effort to further communicate the project results.

4.1.6 PUBLISHING PLATFORMS

Open Research Europe

Open Research Europe (ORE)¹⁸ is an innovative open access publishing platform for the publication of research stemming from Horizon 2020 funding that makes it easy for Horizon 2020 beneficiaries to comply with the open access terms of their funding and offers researchers a publishing venue to share their results and insights rapidly and facilitate open, constructive research discussion. The use of this platform will enable MES-CoBraD involved researchers to publish their research results fast and provide an open peer review that will enhance the project's impact and reach. ORE uses an open research

¹⁵ <http://www.springer.com/computer/swe/journal/10676>

¹⁶ <https://www.ai4eu.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://www.ean.org/>

¹⁸ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

publishing model that supports reproducibility, transparency and impact.

The Innovation Radar

The Innovation Radar¹⁹ is European Commission's data-driven method focused on the identification of high potential innovations and the key innovators behind them in EU-funded Research and Innovation projects. Innovation Radar has the goal of creating a steady flow of promising tech companies that can scale up into future industrial champions. MES-CoBraD through the use of the Innovation Radar will be able to further enhance the role of its platform and provide insight on the projects scope to interested stakeholders and medical industry related companies.

OpenAIRE portal

OpenAIRE²⁰ is a science-related portal, the mission²⁰ of which is to provide unlimited, barrier-free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. The use of OpenAIRE will enable MES-CoBraD, on one hand, to report more effectively and efficiently the scientific, and other, outcomes of the action and, on the other, to reach a wide community of scientists, policymakers, and stakeholders interested in EU-funded research in general. All of the project public deliverables, publications and material, are uploaded in the OpenAIRE portal.

Zenodo

Zenodo²¹ is a general-purpose open access repository developed by CERN within the framework of OpenAIRE, welcoming all science information around the globe, i.e., research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts from every discipline. MES-CoBraD has created a community under Zenodo, in order to provide its outputs in open access and disseminate them to appropriate audiences at the same time. All of the project public deliverables, publications and material, are uploaded in the Zenodo repository. More on the management, processing and maintainability of the action's data and outcomes is available in the respective report, "D2.2 Data management plan".

4.1.7 DATA REPOSITORIES- DATABASES

Although MES-CoBraD will also act as a data repository for study and automatic diagnosis, the following repositories will be considered aiming towards providing access to the scientific community on the project's data and enhancing the project's reach.

Data Europa

Data Europa²² is the point of access to public data published by the EU institutions, agencies and other bodies. The portal is a key instrument of the EU open data strategy with its Information available for commercial or non-commercial purposes. MES-CoBraD could benefit from the established audience of this repository to enhance its presence in the scientific community.

G-Node

G-Node²³ is a web-based secure repository store that you can reach from everywhere that will enable MES-CoBraD sharing data with collaborators or publishing to the greater scientific community.

EBRAINS

¹⁹ <https://www.innoradar.eu/>

²⁰ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

²² <https://data.europa.eu/en>

²³ <https://gin.g-node.org/>

EBRAINS²⁴ provides digital tools and services which can be used to address challenges in brain research and brain-inspired technology development. The tools provided by EBRAINS aim in assisting researchers to collect, analyse, share, and integrate brain data, and to perform modelling and simulation of brain function, and an interaction with MES-CoBraD data may raise awareness on the projects progress and results.

EU Health Data Space

Depending on the level of maturity of the EU Health Data Space²⁵, it may be considered for sharing data with it. The creation of a European Data Space is one of the priorities of the Commission 2019-2025, including the health sector. A common European Health Data Space will promote better exchange and access to different types of health data (electronic health records, genomics data, data from patient registries etc.), not only to support healthcare delivery (so-called primary use of data) but also for health research and health policy making purposes (so-called secondary use of data). MES-CoBraD will investigate the possibilities to integrate its repositories with the service, or individually share data with it.

4.1.8 PARTNERS' WEBSITES/BLOGS

Most partners have websites featuring news on their research activities. In these websites, articles on the progress of MES-CoBraD, as well as announcements on recent reports or upcoming events, have been and will further be published. More particularly, the partners' websites are the NTUA²⁶ partner which is the coordinator of the project, the NIA's²⁷ webpage, the VUB-LSTS²⁸ webpage, the UPS²⁹ university website, the KCL³⁰ website's homepage that features recent news on research progress and upcoming events, while a dedicated webpage for specifically promoting projects' results is also available, SIMAVI³¹ webpage, the LIBER³² website including a specific page dedicated on MES-CoBraD information and news targeting the research library community³³, the ENG³⁴ webpage, the HOLISTIC³⁵ webpage dedicated to news at which developments on MES-CoBraD are featured, the EVOLUTION³⁶ webpage, the University of Edinburgh³⁷ webpage, the CyberEthics Lab³⁸. webpage.

4.1.9 PARTNERS' JOURNALS

LIBER Quarterly

LIBER Quarterly³⁹ is the peer reviewed, open access journal of LIBER, the association of European research libraries. It covers thematises across disciplines that are relevant for research librarians and researchers across Europe. As per its scope, it is "intended as a bridge between the scholars of the LIS departments and the practitioners in university and research libraries. It achieves this by publishing not only theoretical contributions, but also descriptions of examples of good practices".

²⁴ <https://ebrains.eu/service/share-data/>

²⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/health/ehealth/dataspace_en

²⁶ <http://www.epu.ntua.gr>

²⁷ www.nioa.gr

²⁸ <https://lsts.research.vub.be>

²⁹ <https://www.uu.se/>

³⁰ www.kcl.ac.uk/ioppn

³¹ www.simavi.ro

³² libereurope.eu

³³ <https://libereurope.eu/project/mes-cobrad/>

³⁴ [Large Enterprise](http://LargeEnterprise)

³⁵ <https://www.holisticsa.gr/articles-3-col>

³⁶ <https://www.evolutionprojects.gr/>

³⁷ <https://ghpu.sps.ed.ac.uk/>

³⁸ www.cyberethicslab.com

³⁹ <https://www.libquarterly.eu/>

4.1.10 PARTNERS' EVENTS

Partners participate on events organised by the consortium or in joint with other projects and a list of those events is recorded in the monitoring template described in Chapter 10 of this document.

4.1.10.1 MES-CoBraD Workshops

Workshops are small interactive events held to achieve a specific objective. A workshop could be used to get feedback from users on the proposed solution or to get feedback from expert on a particular issue. Within the framework of MES-CoBraD, in the first year all partners have organized and/or attended up to three stakeholder events and workshops which addressed the target communities and the end-users of the MES-CoBraD platform. In the second year of the project, all partners are organising and/or attend to at least three stakeholder events and workshops. Finally, in the third year of the MES-CoBraD project all partners will organize and/or attend to at least three stakeholder events and workshops. There will be a planned participation for all the partners in forthcoming EU Conferences and Workshops. Workshops with other projects of the same EU call are also organised to further disseminate the results of the MES-CoBraD project and to enhance collaboration in the scientific community, raising awareness on the outcomes and developments of the project while serving as a promotion for the upcoming MES-CoBraD platform.

Workshops, as other events, consider health and travel restrictions related to COVID19, hence they are taking place as online events for the first period of the project, aiming to expand to hybrid and/or face-to-face formats later in the project.

4.1.11 EXTERNAL EVENTS

In order to effectively promote MES-CoBraD, partners are encouraged and assisted in the participation in events organised by organisations outside the consortium. This includes the participation in events organised by the European Commission and in other international conferences and workshops in the respective fields so as to keep updated the scientific community, universities, research centres, industry, the EC, policymakers, health scientists and other interested groups. It is envisaged that each partner will participate in at least one event per year.

4.1.11.1 Scientific Conferences

MES-CoBraD partners participate in scientific conferences, in order to disseminate the action to the scientific community by presenting the action's outcomes in a scientific manner.

4.1.11.2 General Conferences

Along the duration of MES-CoBraD project, the partners continuously try to attend conferences and relative meetings of scientific interest focusing on further disseminating the project results and outcomes. This effort will intensify on the last year of the project where the MES-CoBraD platform will launch and will demonstrate the capabilities of the MES-CoBraD solution and tools.

4.1.11.3 Workshops

Several workshops organised by external organisations could be used so as to promote MES-CoBraD. A typical example are several networking events, which are organised for networking among EU-funded projects.

4.1.11.4 Other Events

Apart from conferences and workshops, other events offer opportunities of collaboration with stakeholders, who might be interested in MES-CoBraD's results. These could include commercial exhibitions, anniversary celebration events, etc.

4.1.11.5 Presentations

Partners participating in external events are highly encouraged to deliver presentations on the project's scope, objectives, and expected (or already extracted) results. It is envisaged that more than twenty Internet presentations in academic conferences in at least ten European and non-European countries will be delivered within the project's lifetime.

4.2 SYNERGIES

Creation of synergies with other relevant actions, either funded under Horizon2020 and Horizon Europe or not, is of great importance since it bears many advantages. More particularly, clustering activities increase the outreach potential of the action concepts and raise awareness among a broader spectrum of stakeholders. The plan for creating synergies and promoting collaborations with other projects and initiatives is an important milestone for the project, "MS3 - Identification of opportunity-based promotional activities", the outcomes of which will be presented in detail in the respective report, "D9.8: Final report on opportunity-based promotional activities". Other tools used for clustering activities will be social media and the website. More particularly, the website will contain an External Resources page, listing existing works of other platforms and related projects.

4.3 HORIZON RESULT BOOSTER

Horizon Result Booster⁴⁰ is a new package of specialised services to maximise the impact of R&I public investment and further amplify the added value of a HORIZON 2020 funded project. We consider using the services of this platform for the envelopment of the C&D strategy of MES-CoBraD project since it could speed up the process of creating an impact and provide valuable support to remove bottlenecks. Horizon Result Booster may be equally used in the Exploitation strategy in parallel to the C&D strategy, as it was described in the D9.5 "Business and Exploitation Plan - v1", and further elaborated in this deliverable.

4.4 PROMOTIONAL MEANS

In order to promote MES-CoBraD several promotional materials encapsulating the action's scope, objectives, and expected results are envisaged. Moreover, all the promotional material that will be used will have a simple but distinctive visual identity which has already been created so as to have a consistent and systematic way.

4.4.1 LOGO

To create identity within the consortium and to support "brand recognition" the MES-CoBraD logo was created and will be used in all promotional material. More on the logo can be found in the report "D9.3: Promotional and informational material".

4.4.2 LEAFLET

A promotional leaflet featuring a short project description for dissemination among stakeholders, at conferences and to other interested parties, has been created and constantly updated ever since. In particular, the leaflet briefly describes the project's aims, objectives, contents, expected results, consortium and contact details, and will soon be available in all languages of the consortium members. More on the leaflet can be found in the report "D9.3: Promotional and informational material".

4.4.3 POSTER

A publicity poster regarding MES-CoBraD was designed, updated and printed in order to promote the

⁴⁰ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

action in events organised by the partners or hosted by other relevant organisations. Specifically, the poster briefly describes the action's aims, objectives, contents, expected results, consortium and contact details. More on the poster can be found in the report "D9.3: Promotional and informational material".

4.4.4 MES-CoBRAD PRESENTATION

A standard presentation containing basic information about MES-CoBraD has been produced in order to be used by the partners for dissemination purposes at relevant events. It is envisaged that the presentation will be regularly updated and adapted by the partners on an ad hoc basis, according to the type and size of audience/events where the project will be presented. More on the presentation can be found in the report "D9.3: Promotional and informational material".

4.4.5 ARTICLES

Appropriate articles according to the targeted audience will be disseminated via the aforementioned promotional channels (websites, blogs, etc.). Depending on the desired outcome, these articles may focus on MES-CoBraD and its societal impacts in general or be more specific by promoting individual project outcomes.

4.4.6 REPORTS

MES-CoBraD will produce a number of publicly distributed reports incorporating the results of the implemented research. These reports will be available at the project's website and will be further promoted via social media, newsletters, and other dissemination channels.

4.4.7 WORKING DOCUMENTS

Working documents focus on the output deliverables of MES-CoBraD, which will be consolidated and available in a series of branded reports. Working documents will consist of the main points of the deliverables and will give the main outcomes of the implemented research. They will be distributed in organised events either as hardcopies, or preferably in digital format.

4.4.8 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Scientific publications are one of the keys means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and providing the scientific credibility for the project's work. Scientific publications and policy papers will be published in open access, high-quality, peer-reviewed journals and platforms (e.g., ORE), so as to ensure that the project and its results are made known to the public at large. NTUA will draft a list of topics where published articles would be valuable and journals that might be suitable. The consortium members will sign an agreement for commonly sharing all material produced under MES-CoBraD including scientific publications financed by the project through appropriate open access schemes and archiving it to appropriate repositories.

4.4.9 NEWSLETTERS & ELECTRONIC PROMOTION

4.4.9.1 MES-CoBraD Newsletters

The MES-CoBraD newsletters are used to announce the project, develop a profile, and give regular updates on its progress and developments. The newsletters will be creative, making sure that all target audiences know how the project is progressing. A regular electronic newsletter is issued providing information on the project development and events on a six-monthly basis. The Newsletter incorporates inputs from all partners on progress and key outcomes of the project. Its key aim is to raise awareness about the ongoing work of the action and its relevance to policymaking at EU and national level. The Newsletter is sent to all MES-CoBraD stakeholders as identified throughout the project, as long as they have provided their consent to subscribe to the newsletter. The subscription process complies with the

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which came into force in May 2018. In order to include a person to the newsletter mailing list, a freely given, informed and explicit consent has been given specifically to receive the MES-CoBraD newsletter, while the possibility of withdrawing the consent is clearly explained. Consents are provided either by filling in an online subscription form, by writing the email in the participants list in an organised event, or by direct email in case of personal contacts. It must be noted that these ways may be updated, as necessary.

It is projected that up to 10 e-newsletters will be developed, which will regularly disseminate the project's achievements. The e-newsletters will be developed in English and be translated in all project languages. The e-newsletters in addition to being published on the project's website, so that these are readily accessible by all the target groups across Europe, will be distributed by email to public authorities and other relevant stakeholders in each participating country. The effectiveness of the newsletters' impact will be evaluated by a respective tool and reports, including openings, clicks and list of recipients. Moreover, occasionally press releases may be circulated to various stakeholders and interested parties in case there is a specific need. It is envisaged that at least six press releases will be circulated in non-academic sources.

4.4.9.2 *Infographics*

Due to the information overload, which is a typical characteristic of the latest years, it is very important to use visual means of promotion such as infographics, videos, and presentations. Infographics may be produced during the MES-CoBraD implementation phase, to present various project outcomes.

Appropriately designed infographics will be used to convey to health scientists and other relevant stakeholders the MES-CoBraD results through comprehensive visual representations. Infographics make broad or complex ideas more distilled and simplified and are more eye-catching than printed words, since they combine images, colours, movement, and content.

4.4.9.3 *Videos*

Videos are used in order to disseminate the MES-CoBraD results in a more effective way to appropriate audiences. It is envisaged that a total of three videos targeted at health scientists and other stakeholder groups will be produced and circulated during the project's lifetime. The production of videos will be used to present the project's activities in English. It is foreseen that 5 videos will be produced within the project phase.

5 REPORT ON C&D ACTIVITIES

5.1 WEBSITE

The MES-CoBraD website is online since June 2021. Multiple content has been posted in the website news sections including articles, events announcements and information on the project’s results and outcomes. More than **14** posts are available on the project website and a dedicated section on publications is active as well, linking to the Zenodo and OpenAIRE repositories used to publish the project public reports and deliverables. More than **4,270** users have visited the website, **4,365** sessions were held, including **5,206** pageviews with a bounce rate of **81.56%**.

On the figures below, exported from the Google Analytics, statistics on the website traffic and audience are presented.

Figure 1: Website Traffic analysis

Figure 2: Website users / lifetime

Figure 3: Website traffic origin per communication channel

Top Channels

Figure 4: Website traffic per country of origin

5.1.1 WEBSITE CONTENT SAMPLE

Indicative post of the MES-CoBraD website is presented below.

Figure 5: Website post on partner’s participation in conference in 2022

MES-CoBraD at the “Days of Neurology 2022” conference

Dr. Elissaios Karageorgiou from NIA, was invited at the 12th Panhellenic Conference “Days of Neurology 2022”, which gave the opportunity to present our work on sleep and cognitive disorders, including CBTi in MCI. This work wouldn't be possible without the support of the MES-CoBraD Horizon EU project, the Alzheimer's Association, and GBHI.

The full presentation is available on the video below:

12 Ημέρες Νευρολογίας 2022
3-6 Νοεμβρίου 2022, Καλαμπάκα

Sleep-wake rhythms as harbingers of cognitive decline and degeneration

Circadian advancement and fragmentation

- Earlier melatonin secretion and temperature drop
- 22% faster annual cognitive decline and risk for AD increased by 20-50%

Insomnia prospective studies

Study	Sample Size	Follow-up	Findings
Study 1	1000	12 months	...
Study 2	2000	24 months	...
Study 3	3000	36 months	...

Sleep duration and neurodegeneration

- 30 cognitively normal
- 30-60 vs 1-180 vs MMSE > 27
- CSF at baseline for 24 hours measuring Aβ42, Aβ40 and neurotoxic PDS
- Sleep deprivation increased Aβ40, Aβ42 and Aβ42 levels by 25 to 30%

5.1.2 ZENODO AND OPENAIRE REPOSITORIES

The materials section of the website links to the OpenAIRE and Zenodo repositories where all public reports and deliverables are posted. A total of **37** publications and **1** research dataset are available on

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

both repositories up to date to the scientific community, various stakeholders and the general public.

5.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

The online presence of MES-CoBraD has already been established in Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook. In particular, in Twitter an official MES-CoBraD account has been created while the #MES-CoBraD hashtag is used in every post regarding the action. Moreover, in LinkedIn an organisation webpage has been created in order to disseminate the MES-CoBraD results. Finally, in Facebook account has been created in order to promote the project to the general public. Both direct promotion of the project's beginning (Kick-off meeting, 1st Newsletter, etc.) and a broad, indirect promotion/engagement campaign has been ongoing.

5.2.1 MES-COBRA D TWITTER

MES-CoBraD twitter account is rather active, with **105** followers. All partners post on the MES-CoBraD twitter page and frequent reposts occur, while interesting to the scientific community content is shared and reposted. To date there are more than **639** tweets and retweets, that have gained **10,540** impressions and about **1,400** Engagements.

In the figures below charts on twitter impressions are presented along with some top tweets on the project activities.

Figure 6: Twitter impressions from June 2021 up to September 2021

Figure 7: Twitter impressions from October 2021 up to December 2021

Figure 8: Twitter impressions from January 2022 up to March 2022

Figure 9: Twitter Impressions from April 2022 up to March 2023

5.2.2 MES-CoBRAD FACEBOOK

The MES-CoBraD Facebook page has **68** followers and 15 Post to date. It has reached over **7,165** people that have actively engaged with content presented. The figures below present some indicative traffic analysis for the last year.

Figure 10: Facebook page Reach – lifetime

Figure 11: Facebook page visits lifetime

Figure 12: Facebook page new likes rate – lifetime

The account is more active around project events, enabling the partners to further promote the events and inform the stakeholders and community following.

5.2.3 MES-CoBRAD LINKEDIN

The MES-CoBraD LinkedIn page has over **130** followers from across Europe and the Globe, with **51** new followers on the last **12** months. Most of them originate from Greece, with Italy, Romania, the UK and Netherlands following. The LinkedIn account has performed over **15** posts and multiple reposts, with over **500** page views that gained **3,829** Impressions.

Figure 13: Indicative LinkedIn page visits chart for the last 12 months up to March 2023

5.3 PARTNERS' WEBSITES

Among the partners first CDE activities was an article on the implementation of the MES-CoBraD's kick-off meeting that was published in NTUA's website⁴¹ describing the project, its objective, and the organisation of the kick-off. A Facebook post⁴² on MES-CoBraD was published NTUA's Facebook page as well on the institution's participation on the project. NTUA tweeted⁴³ as well on the project's developments prior to the kick off meeting. In the HOLISTIC news webpage one article featuring MES-CoBraD has already been published⁴⁴, on the project and the role HOLISTIC will play in it.

LIBER has created a specific page⁴⁵, dedicated to MES-CoBraD on its website, as space to share project news and other information (e.g. events, materials, etc) targeting research libraries and relevant

⁴¹ <https://www.epu.ntua.gr/node/449>

⁴² <https://www.facebook.com/epu.ntua.gr/posts/230918048821423>

⁴³ https://twitter.com/DSS_Lab/status/1381525044044554242

⁴⁴ <https://holisticsa.gr/projects/h2020-MES-CoBraD>

⁴⁵ <https://libereurope.eu/project/mes-cobrad/>

stakeholders. Regular information about the project is shared on LIBER's social media, internal mailing lists and LIBER Insider, a monthly mailing targeting the LIBER community.

Multiple other website and social media posts were published by partners on their respective accounts, using the #mescobrad hashtag or a direct reference to the project's SM accounts aiming in further enhancing the projects communication campaign.

Most recently NTUA posted on the impact of RWD and Artificial intelligence in Medical research⁴⁶ and appropriate campaign was launched in the organisations SM.

5.4 MES-COBRA D NEWSLETTERS & VIDEOS

5.4.1 MES-COBRA D NEWSLETTERS

To date three MES-CoBraD newsletters were issued promoting the projects' objectives, activities, achievements and results. These were distributed in English so that they are globally accessible and able to reach the various stakeholders and the global scientific community. A total of 96 active subscribers have enlisted so far through the website subscription form. It should be noted that the MES-CoBraD newsletter is explicitly distributed to subscribers that have registered to receive it through the website form. All of the subscribers' data is kept under GDPR compliance in the newsletter platform's database. The platform used for the newsletter design and issue is Mailerlite⁴⁷. In the table below, the newsletter statistics are presented and in the attached figures, samples of each newsletter are presented.

⁴⁶ [NTUA: LEVERAGING REAL-WORLD DATA AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MEDICAL RESEARCH: THE MES-COBRA D APPROACH](#)

⁴⁷ <https://www.mailerlite.com/>

Table 3: MES-CoBraD Newsletter 1 statistics

Newsletter 1 – December 2021	
Total emails sent:	84
Opened:	33.73%
Clicked:	4.82%

Figure 14: MES-CoBraD Newsletter December 2021 – Sample

Table 4: MES-CoBraD Newsletter 2 statistics

Newsletter 2 – May 2022	
Total emails sent:	96
Opened:	31.18%
Clicked:	2.15%

Figure 15: MES-CoBraD Newsletter May 2022 – Sample

Table 5: MES-CoBraD Newsletter 3 statistics

Newsletter 3 – November 2022	
Total emails sent:	98
Opened:	34.38%
Clicked:	5.21%

Figure 16: MES-CoBraD November 2022 – Sample

5.4.2 PARTNERS' NEWSLETTERS

MES-CoBraD partners often post on the project's developments on their organisation newsletters. LIBER includes updates on the project on its monthly newsletter that is being opened by over **1000** recipients. So far twenty (**20**) LIBER monthly newsletters have been issued including news and updates on the MES-CoBraD project⁴⁸.

Also, RMC-C&E issued a newsletter specifically on the MES-CoBraD project in Hebrew and it was sent in hardcopy version to all of its stakeholders interested. Pictures of the Newsletter are presented below.

⁴⁸ [Sample of a Liber newsletter mentioning MES-CoBraD project \(Feb 2023\)](#)

Figure 17: RMC-C&E Newsletter – Sample

5.4.3 MES-CoBRAD VIDEOS

To date the project has appeared twice on National Greek TV in the O3 tv show and the video recordings are available in the project website. In the first appearance the project goals and expected outcomes were presented⁴⁹, while on the second video recording, the difficulties of the cognitive disorders, the importance of early diagnosis and how the project will assist on was presented⁵⁰.

5.5 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS DEVELOPED

As described in detail in deliverables D9.3 “Promotional and informational material”⁵¹ and D9.4 “Online Materials”⁵², a full spectrum of materials for both printed and electronic sharing have been developed throughout the project’s lifetime. The materials have been further updated to reflect the projects developments and more than 300 leaflets have been printed and delivered throughout the clinical trials in Greece. Also, a specialised poster presenting the data management solutions and practices developed in the project was designed and presented in the 51st LIBER annual conference. The poster won the first place in the contest held during the conference⁵³.

5.6 PUBLICATIONS

Four scientific publications have been issued so far referring to the research conducted in the project and appropriate actions have been taken to further promote their results.

⁴⁹ [MES-CoBraD presented on O3 tech & news show in ERT3 Greece | MES-CoBraD](#)
⁵⁰ [MES-CoBraD on the difficulties of the cognitive disorders on O3 show in ERT3 Greek tv-channel | MES-CoBraD](#)
⁵¹ [D9.3 on Zenodo](#)
⁵² [D9.4 on Zenodo](#)
⁵³ [Data management in the MES-CoBraD project: What’s in it for research libraries – POSTER PRESENTATION – LIBER CONFERENCE. | MES-CoBraD](#)

5.7 ORGANIZATION OF EVENTS

5.7.1 KICK-OFF MEETING, 12-13 APRIL 2021, ATHENS, GREECE

MES-CoBraD's Kick-off Meeting was successfully remotely organised via Teams, on the 13th of April 2021. Participants had the opportunity to remotely meet with each other, overview the project's expectations and discuss the challenges of the forthcoming tasks. In total 45 people from 9 countries attended the meeting. The event featured several insightful presentations by highly qualified experts setting the tone for the actions that will follow during the coming months, as well as the strategic planning for the duration of the project.

5.7.2 MES FOR THE COBRAD WORKSHOP

A workshop was organised on the 6th of May 2021 focusing on the RWD types and their high-level categorization as they are acquired by the partners. The RWD structures and protocols and the main themes of clinical research and data analysis. Partners participated online and provided feedback on all panels. The event was disseminated through the project's SM accounts.

5.7.3 1ST PROJECT MEETING - WORKSHOP

The project's first project meeting was held in person in Bucharest in the 20-21st of October 2021 and apart from the progress per WP presentations and discussions, it included a discussion on the User stories and the AI/Analytics to be implemented in the project, in the form of a partners' workshop.

5.7.4 BMC WORKSHOP

An online interactive workshop was organised on the 31st of January 2022 aiming to engage the partners in the process of co-drafting the business model to be applied on the MES-CoBraD project.

5.7.5 MES-CoBRAD POSTER IN LIBER CONFERENCE

The 51st edition of the LIBER conference was held from 6th – 8th July in Odense, and MES-CoBraD RWD solutions were presented through a specifically developed poster. The poster participated in a contest held among 12 other projects and won the 1st place⁵⁴.

5.7.6 MES-CoBRAD JOINT PROJECTS' WEBINAR

Project partners participated on the Joint Public Webinar organised between MES-CoBraD, RETENTION and RE-SAMPLE projects and introduced their work and discussed shared challenges in applying data intensive models, utilising machine learning, for improved healthcare outcomes⁵⁵.

5.7.7 MES-CoBRAD AT THE "DAYS OF NEUROLOGY 2022" CONFERENCE

Dr Elissaios Karageorgiou from NIA was invited at the 12th Panhellenic Conference "Days of Neurology 2022", which gave the opportunity to present our work on sleep and cognitive disorders, including CBTi in MCI. This work wouldn't be possible without the support of the MES-CoBraD Horizon EU project, the Alzheimer's Association, and GBHI⁵⁶.

5.7.8 2ND, 3RD, 4TH PROJECT MEETING

Three more project meetings were organised throughout the last 22 months in the project, either online

⁵⁴ [Data management in the MES-CoBraD project: What's in it for research libraries – POSTER PRESENTATION – LIBER CONFERENCE. | MES-CoBraD](#)

⁵⁵ [MES-CoBraD Webinar | MES-CoBraD](#)

⁵⁶ [MES-CoBraD at the "Days of Neurology 2022" conference | MES-CoBraD](#)

or in person where multiple issues were addressed, and partners were able to engage in multiple discussions on the project outcomes and planning.

5.7.9 CDE PLANNING WORKSHOP

An online interactive workshop was organised on the 10th of March 2022 enabling the partners to actively assess the new actions and goals for the CDE strategy of the project, taking into consideration the parameters set for the development of the project's business model.

5.7.10 OTHER EVENTS

Internal Project Events are being planned for the near future while all partners are actively engaging in public and scientific events aiming to further disseminate and communicate the project outcomes and results.

6 EXPLOITATION OUTCOMES

This is the second version of the MES-CoBraD Business and Exploitation document. The first version “D9.5. Exploitation, Business, and Exploitation Plan v-1” that was submitted before in March 2022, briefly presented the MES-CoBraD project outcomes and the overall exploitation plan that the entire consortium should follow. This version is updated and describes more clearly the MES-CoBraD exploitable outcomes since we are on month 24 of the project with all the components having their first version developed. In this section, we describe in detail the MES-CoBraD key exploitable outcomes (the platform itself, the Pilot Use Cases, the Policy Recommendations and the Scientific and Technical Knowledge), their respective goals and needed actions to be achieved, that this exploitation and sustainability plan is focused on. Exploitable outcomes will be updated in future versions of this deliverable (D9.7). The key exploitable outcomes of the MES-CoBraD project are the following:

6.1 MES-COBRA D PLATFORM

6.1.1 DESCRIPTION

MES-CoBraD major exploitable technical outcome is the MES-CoBraD Platform itself, which supports multiple-type data sharing by creation, sanitization, anonymization, harmonization and upload of datasets providing tools for harmonized data collection and analysis through a single common data-lake environment. Clinical history, questionnaires and scales, neurophysiology and neuroimaging data can be used. Several open-source and tailor-made tools are included, designed to address advanced research needs.

The platform integrates several general statistical functions and machine learning algorithms, based on the acquired data, and used in a workflow management system, forming an expert system to support research and diagnostic processes. Users without significant technical experience or available computational resources will be able to share, review and analyze their data in a unified ecosystem. The MES-CoBraD platform is secure, and users will equitably have access to the entire database depending on their license. The platform will give access to users according to the validation and acceptance of the administrators (technical partners) depending on the settings selected per module and component.

The MES-CoBraD platform will not only offer solutions and models, but also anonymized and depersonalized open data, according to the user’s license.

There will be two types of quality products to be exploited:

- The first one is Open-Source modules, to which the user can integrate their multidimensional data.
- The second one is the module to upload data into the Platform’s datalake; in this module, the key element is on deciding by the settings how data will be included in the Platform.

Figure 18: MES-CoBraD platform architecture

The services that the MES-CoBraD platform gives to the users are easily adapted, or embedded into available medical, clinical or health infrastructures. Furthermore, the MES-CoBraD platform embeds an innovative architecture to improve early diagnosis, provide more accurate prognosis, and identify optimal therapies in Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as represented in neurocognitive (dementia), seizure and sleep disorders. The MES-CoBraD platform aims at a society where patients and caregivers have the opportunity for the best possible quality of life irrespective of their health and socioeconomic background.

MES-CoBraD innovative technology is expected to:

- › Improve clinical prognosis using supervised and unsupervised advanced analytics artificial intelligence models,
- › Enhance the platform with the use of Real-World Data.
- › Build a certified and trust platform through advanced usable transparency tools derived from health and care personnel.

6.1.2 EXPLOITATION GOALS

In this section, we present a summary of the main exploitation objectives for the MES-CoBraD Platform, and the actions needed to fulfill these objectives.

Table 6: Exploitation objectives for the MES-CoBraD platform

Exploitation Goal	Actions Needed
Exploit the business potential of the MES-CoBraD platform and enhance its viability extending the project lifetime.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Develop the MES-CoBraD business model plan. › Receive feedback from the pilot use cases regarding the sustainability and exploitation potential of the platform. › Disseminate the MES-CoBraD platform and its value to a wide target

audience (customers, and stakeholders).

6.2 MES-COBRA D PILOT USE CASES

Four inter-related Pilot Uses Cases (PUC) will be pursued to advance scientific knowledge in CoBraD, serve as examples of the exploitation potential of the MES-CoBraD Platform, maximizing novelty and impact, and highlighting the platform's integration potential of multisource RWD for diverse clinical-research projects in CoBraD through its abstract methodology. Each PUC will address clinical, research, and technological challenges faced in medicine, and especially in CoBraD and each PUC is an indicative case of the MES-CoBraD project's Expected Impact, as called for by the Work Program. To better understand the exploitation potential of each pilot, a brief description follows.

6.2.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOTS

Table 7: MES-CoBraD pilot activities

Pilots	Description
PUC 1: MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Multisource Real-World Data Assessment Protocol	Is a representative case of how the MES-CoBraD Platform will integrate RWD, addressing several of the clinical, research and technological challenges and the expected impact that the work programme calls for.
PUC 2: MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Deep-Phenotyping and Prognostication	Highlights the potential of MES-CoBraD Platform in advancing the precision medicine through advances analytic modules.
PUC3: MES-CoBraD Real-World Therapy Repurposing and Approved Indication Reassessment	Assesses the MES-CoBraD Platform cross-sectionally and longitudinally in assessing clinical outcomes in relation to established therapies in real-world practice.
PUC4: Development and Validation of a Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders – MES-CoBraD	Focuses on the development of the Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment and Management of CoBraD and its cross-validation throughout the project's lifetime.

As far as the Pilot use case 1, the clinical protocol, which is integrated, is running, and even though the platform tools are not in use so far, the analytics are done with varied results, depending on hypothesis testing. Furthermore, the infrastructure for running a clinical trial and collecting the data is ready. Pilot use Case 1 consists of implementing complex clinical and research protocols combined with harmonizing RWD and allowing, through the analytics tools, where Pilot use case 2 comes in, to deeply phenotype the complex brain disorders, or other medical conditions, for diagnosis and treatment decisions. Pilot use case 3 follows with assessing clinical outcomes related to and compared with established therapies in real-world practice and evaluating them. In Pilot use case 4, all the above information will be used through the clinical expert system in guiding users (clinicians who need a decision, diagnosis and management, support system) to the next steps.

Detailed description of the pilot activities is included in “D8.2: MES-CoBraD Validation Framework.”⁵⁷ The exploitation of the pilot use cases is a key process of the project because will record the deployment of the platform.

6.3 POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

6.3.1 DESCRIPTION

MES-CoBraD research and development activities will result to policy recommendations and best practices that should be exploited by the key policy makers and stakeholders. In the project, the Work Package 4 allows for identifying policy recommendations and the Work Package 9 is responsible for disseminating them. The exploitation plan will focus on identifying key policies that should be promoted and disseminated to the key policy makers and stakeholders, regarding the Pilot Use Cases results.

6.3.2 EXPLOITATION GOALS

In this section the aim is to develop a policy recommendation and support dialogue with the policy makers and the stakeholders at the EU and at national level, aiming at increasing the policy investments to the platform and the cyber protection of the Real-World data.

Table 8: Exploitation objectives for MES-CoBraD policy recommendations

Exploitation Goal	Actions Needed
Develop policy recommendations that are re-usable and can be applied to other similar projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Develop policy recommendations, best practices based on the outcomes of the MES-CoBraD project, especially on the outcomes of the pilot use cases. › Engage in active dialogue with policymakers, presenting the solutions implemented in MES-CoBraD addressing known issues on medical data research

6.4 SCIENTIFIC & TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE

6.4.1 DESCRIPTION

As already presented in the deliverable “D1.2: Scientific, Technical and Innovation Roadmap”, one of the main goals of the MES-CoBraD project is to create a scientific and innovation roadmap that provides steps that are necessary to achieve the MES-CoBraD scope, vision and guidelines to provide help to healthcare providers, industry, companies, hospitals and scientists who can improve the patient’s life, innovation and competitiveness. The scientific roadmap focuses on the necessary steps for realizing the optimum use of RWD, techniques, services, toolkits and methodologies of the MES-CoBraD Platform. In order for MES-CoBraD to realise successfully its vision within a scientific and social framework, a set of objectives are set throughout its duration as well as the exploitation of the project’s results after its end. The overall project success will be defined by the efficiency and effectiveness of the appropriate synthesis, as well

⁵⁷ [D8.2 on Zenodo](#)

as the individual quality of the specific achievements related to the project's objectives, clearly measured by key performance indicators. Scientific and Societal Objectives will be pursued in tandem with Technological Objectives (see respective chapter) to maximise impact and chance of success. Scientific and social objectives have the following traits:

- › **Scientific objectives** focus on the scientific work that will be pursued to deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles.
- › **Societal objectives** focus on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the gained spread of the excellence, the expansion of its ecosystem, and the real-life sustainability.

In the table below, the Exploitation goals of MES-CoBraD project, which are further defined in section 9, are presented. Specific actions to be taken by the Partners involved will be co-designed with them and presented on the last version of the CDE report D9.7.

Table 9: Exploitation objectives for the MES-CoBraD scientific, technical and educational knowledge

Exploitation Goal	Partners involved
New and improved scientific, technical, and educational knowledge	Three educational infrastructures to be improved (NTUA, Uppsala, University of Edinburgh)
Attaching added value to on-going innovation, providing demonstrators built during the MES-CoBraD project implementation to engage public administrations, bringing pioneer ideas and knowledge to university students that will impact their academic work (PhD dissertation, post-Doc, papers, etc.) along with the practical experience obtained	NTUA
Adding value to ongoing research that relate to the field of neuroscience and neurology, encouraging future or present university students to engage in research related to the ideas proposed in the PROJECT	Uppsala University
UE expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project in multiple dimensions, including exploiting added value to other research projects	University of Edinburgh

7 MES-COBRA D BUSINESS CASES FOR EXPLOITATION

7.1 INTRODUCTION

The MES-CoBraD business cases outline why the target market would be interested in the MES-CoBraD toolkit, what would be the benefit the market will gain from the results, and how the business models will create the bridge between the Consortium and the target audience, aiming at bringing the appropriate results to the market by the development of the MES-CoBraD business plan.

7.2 PLAN FOR EXPLOITING THE MES-COBRA D PLATFORM

Three phases will be implemented in order to realise the MES-CoBraD exploitation and sustainability potential. These are the following:

- › Business Model exploration,
- › Business Model experimentation,
- › Business Model implementation.

7.2.1 BUSINESS MODEL EXPLORATION

Business model exploration phase aims at generating value propositions, inspired by the matching of the MES-CoBraD outcomes to the unsatisfied market needs and gaps. These value propositions will be used as core components for the business models that will be developed in the next phase, namely “Business model experimentation”.

The aim of the Business model exploration phase was to identify the market trends, gaps and opportunities, and to produce a strategy for positioning the MES-CoBraD toolkit and the MES-CoBraD components in the market. It began towards the middle of the second-year project and an extensive market analysis may follow if necessary, while considering the MES-CoBraD project outcomes. The main goal of the Business model exploration is to set the exploitation ground and thus challenge project partners to produce the project’s main market targets and value propositions. The main market targets of the MES-CoBraD platform are the clinicians, the medical researchers, pharma and health tech industries, patients with CoBraD diseases, the European Union, Policymakers and the AI researchers. For all these markets, the state of play can be researched and presented to find the value proposition of its customer. More specifically, in this phase the key players are identified, the market dynamics will be illustrated and the key performance indicators (KPIs) of the market can be discussed. These can be combined with KPIs of the MES-CoBraD Project to identify a most useful business model. The results of the business model exploration phase will be presented in the business model in the market analysis section.

7.2.2 BUSINESS MODEL EXPERIMENTATION

In the business model experimentation phase, the value proposition for its customer is suggested, identified and the preliminary business model is developed. For this purpose, so far in the project lifetime, 2 workshops were organised, where partners discussed and defined alternative value propositions from the MES-CoBraD outcomes. The value propositions were used to create the MES-CoBraD business model, validate the assumptions of the outcomes and their underlying logic and purpose. In the first workshop, each partner of the consortium had the opportunity to give its feedback on the value propositions and then all partners voted for the most applicable one. On the second workshop, an analysis of the possible exploitation outcomes of the project was conducted by all and the exploitation strategy and actions for the last year of the project was decided, leading to the final sustainability plan.

7.2.2.1 Business modelling Workshop

The first workshop was held on the 31st of January 2022 and aimed to activate all the partners in providing valuable feedback and their business ideas, considering their expertise and activities in our project. For this purpose, we used the specialised organisational platform Mural⁵⁸, which enabled us to present the guidelines and the aim of the workshop along with a contained interactive environment for live collaboration under the guidance of HOLISTIC. The participants identified the value propositions of the MES-CoBraD outcomes and drafted the Business model of the MES-CoBraD project. The partners voted the key points to create a business model canvas which incorporates the ideas and value propositions of the project.

The value propositions are:

- › Deep phenotyping of CoBraD and their interrelations will significantly improve clinical care in people with CoBraD diseases.
- › Identification of impactful treatments or side effects of the CoBraD diseases.
- › Epidemiological insight for future (executive) decisions.
- › AI-assisted diagnosis.
- › Analysis of combinations of multiple datasets.
- › Clinical Decision Support Systems.
- › Secure and anonymised sharing of Real-World Data.

Figure 19: MES-CoBraD workshop sample picture of platform used for the BMC drafting.

⁵⁸ <https://www.mural.co/>

7.2.2.2 *Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities Report and Plan Workshop*

The second workshop was held on the 10th of March 2023 and aimed not only to report all the partners with the updated information about the so far actions, but also to activate them in valuable feedback and their business ideas, considering their expertise and activities in our project. The participants reevaluate and prioritize the value propositions of the MES-CoBraD outcomes and drafted the Business model's second version of the MES-CoBraD project. The partners voted on the key points to update the business model canvas, which incorporates the ideas and value propositions of the project. During this workshop, in addition, to being informed by the presentation itself, partners had the opportunity to interact through the specialized polling platform, Mentimeter⁵⁹, under the guidance of Holistic, prioritize their choices of each canvas category and elements (key partners, activities, resources etc.) and add their suggestions towards that (as presented in the below figures). In the business model canvas (v2) presented in figure 26, all the categories and elements are presented, in the order that they were categorized by the consortium.

⁵⁹ <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

Figure 20: CDE Interactive Workshop, Customer Segments Question

Figure 21: CDE Interactive Workshop, Value Propositions Question

Could you prioritize the must-be-done Key Activities to make the business model work?

Mentimeter

13

Figure 22: CDE Interactive Workshop, Key Activities Question

Could you prioritize the project's crucial Key Partners?

Mentimeter

12

Figure 23: CDE Interactive Workshop, Key Partners Question

Could you prioritize the project's required Key Resources?

Mentimeter

13

Figure 24: CDE Interactive Workshop, Key Resources Question

Could you prioritize the project's C&D Channels?

Mentimeter

13

Figure 25: CDE Interactive Workshop, C&D Channels Question

7.2.2.3 Customer Segments

MES-CoBraD business potential as identified during the workshops can directly split in four different stakeholder groups: (a) CoBraD Healthcare domain (clinical researchers, clinicians, pharma industries), (b) patients with CoBraD and their caregivers, (c) IoT industry (AI researchers and data scientists), (d)

CoBraD researchers. Regulators/Polymakers will be also engaged because they are the key stakeholders who influence the market, indirectly benefiting from the Project's results, albeit not as direct users of the MES-CoBraD Platform. Media outlets will be informed of the latest research on CoBraD and will obtain a concrete framework to discuss labour social policies, such as the relationship between productivity and purchasing power or continuous workforce education, considering trained experts will need to constantly update their skillset in using advanced analytics tools.

7.2.2.3.1 CoBraD Healthcare Scientists, Researchers, Clinicians and Organisations

The need for a new top-down approach has emerged from the research that is being done on the relevant field, to enable clinical researchers, scientists and medical researchers to identify CoBraD patients from an early stage. So far, increased technological developments enable the early diagnoses of CoBraD diseases, however tools for modelling the prediction of such diseases are lacking as well as the Real-World Data that need to be leveraged. At the same time, clinicians are missing said tools, so they are lacking the means to efficiently monitor CoBraD patients as they do not have comprehensive and useful databases to keep track of them.

The MES-CoBraD platform will enable this process by being an open platform in which all the potential customers can identify and access real-world clinical and social data from patients and their caregivers through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast clinical protocols, leveraging scientific research in CoBraD and technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms of Artificial Intelligence, Advanced Analytics, and Expert Systems towards precision and personalised care. Naturally, the success of the MES-CoBraD platform is dependent also on the hospital staff's, and patients' and caregivers' willingness to change the way they use the systems that will improve their purpose and increase data privacy and integrity.

Hence, the platform and its outcomes address Healthcare Scientists, Researchers, Clinicians and Organisations, both as their potential users (customers) and as co-developers/modulators/creators of the whole project.

7.2.2.3.2 Pharma Industry

In addition to identifying possible complex brain disorders and their diagnosis, the MES-CoBraD platform's purpose is also to suggest possible treatments and their side effects. Therefore, during the second workshop, the consortium recognized the pharmaceutical industry as a significant customer segment to correlate not only at the stages of designing and development but also at the stages of testing, implementation, and commercialization.

7.2.2.3.3 Patients and Caregivers

CoBraD patients and healthcare personnel are potential "customers" per se since they could vastly benefit from the potential improvement of the diagnosis process and the identification of possible treatment combinations and practices with the use of the advanced analytics implemented in the MES-CoBraD platform toolkit. The RWD provided by the patients and caregivers are essential to the development of the platform itself and a mutual beneficiary relationship could be established.

7.2.2.3.4 IoT Industry

Industry at the IoT and security sector are an important market actor of the MES-CoBraD Platform such as:

- › Industry producing digital wearables and IoT services, such as wrist-worn activity trackers incorporating heart rate and other physiologic biomarkers targeting consumers.
- › Industry producing communication devices and enabling devices, such as tablets and phones that collect consumer health info.
- › Cyber security providers, software development industry producing the applications that

analyse Real-World Data.

- › Cyber security practitioners, experts in the security domain from software development industry.

7.2.2.3.5 Artificial Intelligence Researchers

AI researchers are another particularly important market actor of the MES-CoBraD platform because they can analyse RWD and give the customers of the Platform useful insights about the results of all the above tools, as well as provide the opportunity to patients and their caregivers to pursue a better quality of life, irrespective of their health and socioeconomic background.

7.2.2.3.6 Regulators/ Policymakers/EU

Regulators and Policymakers in the Health sector are important lobbying actors because they can put pressure in decision-making procedures. Additionally, they help define long-term regulations to ensure stability in the market while setting the framework for business models to be aligned to relevant regulations.

The most crucial information for Regulators and Policymakers is how the market reacts to reliable simulations. The MES-CoBraD Project, through the application of technology on RWD, will be able to provide technical and financial information along with the health and social impact of that information.

MES-CoBraD will also investigate improvements and alternatives to current institutional and governance frameworks in order to improve healthcare awareness and stimulate the usage of the proposed solution aiming to empower the life of people with CoBraD.

7.2.3 MES-COBRA D BUSINESS MODEL IMPLEMENTATION

The MES-CoBraD Consortium will develop and validate the business model for the MES-CoBraD Platform. The business models will describe how a subject can create, deliver and capture value by taking advantage of the MES-CoBraD Platform. An updated business model, to that presented in D9.5, has been drafted by the Consortium and the second version was finalised during the workshop that was held on the 10th of March 2023. This business model (v2.0) that is presented in Figure 26 will function as a basis for the final business models that will be developed at the end of the project. The MES-CoBraD business models that will be developed will be the result of:

- › A thorough examination of the available business models/strategies for open-source platforms and their multiple variations.
- › A business modelling workshop that conducted in MES-CoBraD where all consortium partners were be present.
- › A thorough feedback that we will aim to receive from experts in the field where we will have the opportunity to pitch the MES-CoBraD business model. The core MES-CoBraD business model will be presented and validated during an event that will be organised by the MES-CoBraD Consortium.

Based on the identified business models (the second version being in the figure 19 below and the first version in D9.5) the MES-CoBraD business and exploitation plan will be developed. The MES-CoBraD 2nd business model is presented below using the Business Model Canvas⁶⁰ methodology:

⁶⁰ <https://miro.com/templates/business-model-canvas/>

Business Model Canvas		Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
		MES-CobraD	HOLISTIC	10/3/2023	0.2
Key Partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Clinicians > Clinical Researchers > ICT Medical Researchers > MES-CobraD patients/Caregivers > EU and other public funding collaboration > Software and hardware > AI open-source communities > Infrastructure provider(s) > Media 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Continuous RWData integration and Data infrastructure > Improvement of the platform and tools > Improvement of Expert System algorithm > Disseminate the platform's research output > Keep up-to-date guidelines and clinical protocols > Responsive to feedback from users 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Clinical Decision Support System-ES > Secure and anonymize sharing of the Real World Data > Deep phenotyping of CobraD and their interrelations will significantly improve clinical care in people with CobraD > Analysis of combinations of multiple datasets > Identification of impactful treatments or side effects > Epidemiological insight for future (executive) decisions > AI based diagnosis 	Customer Relationships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Producing research results > Data sharing between organisations/Shared Analysis > Clinicians providing services to their patients > High quality research results for the AUT community > Act as a respiratory of good practices for the medical community 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Clinicians > Medical Researchers > Pharma and Health Tech Industry > Patients with CobraD > European Union > Policymakers > AI Researchers > Media 	
	Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Real-World-Data sources and repositories > Human Resources such as Doctors, Patients, Caregivers, Stakeholders, Researchers > Intellectual Properties such as client databases, clinical trials & research data > IT Infrastructure/GPUs/CPUs/Disk space 		Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Scientific publications > Conferences & Lectures > Educational activities to the public (events, demonstrations and material) > Social Media > MES-CobraD Platform > Existing customers-word of mouth > User manuals, tutorials, e-learning material > Newsletters 		
Cost Structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Marketing > Helpdesk costs > Administrative accounting > Engineering costs > Scientific Advisor cost > Database and platform upkeep costs > GPU/CPU > Subscription fees for use of Platform tools for researchers > Platform fees for Clinicians performing diagnosis/treatment > Health Policy implementation grants > Health Insurance companies-paying for anonymised data provision 		Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > "Pay in Data" scenarios > Subscription fees for use of Platform tools for researchers > Platform fees for Clinicians performing diagnosis/treatment > Health Policy implementation grants > Health Insurance companies-paying for anonymised data provision 			

Figure 26: MES-CoBraD BMC (v2)

Starting from the “Customer Segments” for whom we are delivering the value (and would be willing to pay for the MES-CoBraD product), the consortium identified and prioritized the following types of customers: a) Public and Private Healthcare organizations (Clinicians, Health Networks), b) Medical Researchers c) Pharma and Health Tech Industry d) Patients with CoBraD e) European Union f) Policymakers g) AI Researchers and h) Media. During the second workshop, it was suggested to add the EU Data Spaces as a potentially targeted segment, including EuroRec (European Institute for Health Records).

Moving to the “Value propositions” segment which is the value that we are delivering to our customers and the needs that we are satisfying, MES-CoBraD provides (in the order that the consortium categorized them) a) a Clinical Decision Support System-ES, b) a secure and anonymize sharing system of the Real World Data, c) an intercorrelation between the deep phenotyping CoBraD and the people with CoBraD diseases, d) analysis of combinations of multiple datasets, e) identification of impactful treatments or side effects, f) AI based diagnosis epidemiological insights for future decisions. Additionally, the consortium recognized the importance of matching each key exploitable result with correlated targeted Customer Segments.

The customer relationships as these are defined by the MES-CoBraD consortium are: a) Long-term, meaning that MES-CoBraD will interact with the customers on a recurring basis, b) Personal assistance meaning that the customer can communicate with MES-CoBraD after a purchase is complete (onsite, through email, call centers etc.), c) training sessions, workshops and pitch events that will be organised for the customers by MES-CoBraD.

Every business model requires Key Resources to run, thus in MES-CoBraD the consortium identified: a) Real-World-Data sources and repositories, b) Human resources. such as Doctors, Patients, Caregivers, Stakeholders, Researchers. for research, development and support, c) Human resources for marketing purposes, d) Intellectual Properties such as client databases, clinical trials & research data e) IT Infrastructure/GPUs/CPUs/Disk space.

The most critical key activities, as recognized and prioritized during the recent workshop, that MES-CoBraD must do to make its business model work are: a) Further and continuous RWD integration and Data infrastructure development, testing, and validation, b) Improvement of the platform, the Expert System algorithm and the related tools, c) Disseminate the platform's research output, d) Keep up-to-date guidelines and clinical protocols and e) Responsive to feedback from users. Moreover, partners described the need to detail and specify the different activities involved with each outcome after their collaboration.

The business model could be implemented by the following key partners: a) MES-CoBraD consortium (mainly the developers of the components and the business experts willing to take up the results), b) Clinicians, c) Clinical Researchers, d) ICT Medical Researchers, e) MES-CoBraD patients/Caregivers, f) EU and other public funding collaboration, g) Software and hardware, h) AI open-source communities, i) Infrastructure provider(s), j) Media.

MES-CoBraD communicates with and reaches the customers to deliver the value proposition in the following ways, according to the definition and prioritization of the consortium's workshop: a) Scientific publications, b) Conferences & Lectures, c) Educational activities to the public (events, demonstrations, and material designing and production), d) Social Media e) MES-CoBraD Platform, f) Existing customers-word of mouth g) User manuals, tutorials, e-learning material h) Newsletters The key resources / activities which are most expensive (cost structure): The costs that are important to operate the MES-CoBraD business model are the following: a) Development and integration costs, b) Marketing and Sales costs, d) Infrastructure and GPU/CPU costs, e) database and platform upkeep costs, etc.

The revenue streams that represent the way MES-CoBraD will generate cash from the customers are the following: a) Subscription fees for use of Platform tool for Researchers, b) "Pay in Data" scenarios, c) Health insurance companies- paying for anonymized data provision.

7.3 PLAN FOR EXPLOITING THE MES-COBRA D COMPONENTS

The process of identifying potential business models for the individual components of the MES-CoBraD project has already started in the D1.2 'Scientific, Technical and Innovation Roadmap' which was the innovation management phase of the project. The innovation management phase assisted the MES-CoBraD partners in eliciting insights for building potential business cases for their individual components. Towards this notion, webinars, workshops, Q&As meetings are foreseen where the exploitation and the innovation management team will guide the partners on identifying the value of their components in order to fulfil the project's purpose. For the components that do have clear commercialisation potential, technical partners with the assistance of the exploitation team will build appropriate business models. The process of building a business case from individual components is the following:

1. Gather feedback from "D1.2 Scientific and Innovation Roadmap" and record the key points.
2. Exploitation options from all the discussions in the meetings that already took place during the project.
3. Bilateral discussions between the exploitation and innovation management team and the nine technical partners (NTUA, NIA, IR-HSCSP, SIMAVI, EVOLUTION) leading the development of the components.
4. For the partners interested in commercialising their outcomes, work on identifying appropriate business models.
5. The workshops that took place targeted to technical and scientific partners where the process of building a business model was explained.

8 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

8.1 CONTEXT

MES-CoBraD is a secure, privacy-respectful, modular platform that can be integrated with other platforms or be used as a standalone for using its independent analytics modules on the RWD stored in its secure MES-CoBraD Data Lake. The MES-CoBraD Platform and its associated components, evaluated in the course of four different pilot use cases will be available at TRL6 and will be possible to be commercially exploited after the project's completion. More specifically, it is worth to mention that MES-CoBraD is not only designed to deliver scientific and technical assets but also other important exploitable results, such as data and knowledge that can be further exploited in the form of business services: from consultancy, business analytics, customisation, update or development of new features in a service.

Overall, to achieve the long-term exploitation/sustainability goal, the MES-CoBraD Project and its proposed model is seeking to become a reference tool in the field and framework for understanding the socio-economic impact of its results at European and international level. For this, the consortium is striving to meet the needs of the scientific communities and the stakeholders involved with policy demand for socio-economic impact assessment (funding agencies; policy makers and local, national, and regional authorities).

A critical condition for sustainability will be the willingness of the specific scientific community to continue to update the model beyond the life of the project. A vital role in this sustainability is the continuous interaction with the project's experts' group. We foresee several concrete options for the sustainability of the project after finalisation. The table below summarises the major exploitable items related to the MES-CoBraD research framework and data infrastructure solution along with the lead partners and main stakeholders involved.

The following table presents the relevant stakeholder groups for each potential exploitation outcome and is directly linked with the outcomes of WP3 on stakeholder engagement. The progress of each component will be monitored to further enhance the exploitation potential and stakeholder targeting.

Table 10: Exploitable Items related to the MES-CoBraD research framework and data infrastructure solution along with the main stakeholders

Exploitable Outcome	Targeted Stakeholders
MES-CoBraD Integrated Clinical Research Platform	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Pharma & Medical Informatics Industry, Policymakers, Health Providers.
MES-CoBraD research database	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Research Funding Organisation, Pharma & Medical Informatics Industry, Policymakers, Citizen Scientists, Healthcare Organisations, and Health Insurance.
MES-CoBraD Services Stack	Research Performing Organisations, Research Funding Organisation, Pharma & Medical Informatics Industry.
MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Modules (e.g., stand-alone Expert Systems Module, Data Analytics and Visualisation service, AI-based modules)	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Health Providers.
ETHAI model	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Health Providers.

Regarding the timeline, the MES-CoBraD Communication & Sustainability strategy is structured in three main phases as they are presented in the below figure.

Figure 27: MES-CoBraD CDE Strategy

Currently we are focusing on the implementation of the preliminary communication strategy, the agreement on the respective future activities of the Project, and the launching of initial awareness in the markets related to the Project's objectives and scope. The present phase is followed by the second phase, which aims to create more 'target awareness' regarding the MES-CoBraD technologies with the key players and potential users and inform the target market about the technological benefits of MES-CoBraD. Finally, the third phase aims at maximizing the target market and industry awareness regarding the MES-CoBraD platform, thus contributing to ensuring the project sustainability and whole exploitation plan of the Project.

8.2 METHODOLOGY

The MES-CoBraD Consortium is implementing the Project with the vision to prepare the ground and reach sustainability goals. Partners of common organisation types work collaboratively towards the different goals:

1. Pilot organisations maintain the MES-CoBraD Platform: All the appropriate IT organisations of the consortium work collaboratively to develop the MES-CoBraD platform that is being to deliver to end-user partners. The testing period of the platform is approximately ready to be initiated and they will assess the platform in their replicated real environments, against targeted risks and threats including combined cyber and physical attacks. In parallel, end-user partners will also monitor and control the risks, threats and incidents in terms of reliability of the real-world data. In this way, end-user organisations will validate the platform and communicate the findings of the pilot operation of the services with the IT organisation to improve the MES-CoBraD platform initial deployment to prepare an outlook for its large-scale usability. As a result, by the end of the project the MES-CoBraD Platform will be assessed in replicated real environments but will not be ready to be installed and run at hospitals within daily routine operations. Further research and development will need to be conducted to increase its TRL level. In this respect, during the project progress, partners will agree on a partnership that will act to find the funding to continue the research work and pilot demonstration.
2. Verify the business potential of the MES-CoBraD platform: IT industry and all the partners co-design with the exploitation manager the MES-CoBraD business models. The 2nd edition of these is presented in the current C&D&E plan and report. To increase the business potential, partners is decided take actions to present the business models at the targeted audience in order to receive feedback and verify that MES-CoBraD proposed approach meets their needs. In addition, MES-CoBraD consortium is aiming to get benefit of the strong demonstrations that will be implemented

within the project timeframe, and present to the potential market the benefits of the MES-CoBraD platform and its components in replicated real environment conditions.

3. Further usage of the other exploitable outcomes: A rich property of scientific knowledge will be produced during the project implementation through the mature research that experienced partners will conduct in this innovative discipline of models with RWD in the health sector. Partners from universities and research centres will take the necessary actions to expand this knowledge to other researchers and clinicians, progressing the field of CoBraD. In addition, evidenced based policy recommendations will be outlined from the pilot demonstrations. Partners from public authorities will communicate such information at EU and national level.
4. Monitoring of potential partners' interest and involving them: All partners have to record and monitor communications with the agencies, companies, organizations, and individuals, relevant to the fields of related sciences and areas of the project, that expressed interest (due to the implemented C&D plan) to contribute to the program, in order to increase its potential.

9 PARTNERS' INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION PLANS

9.1 CONSORTIUM MEMBERS' EXPLOITATION PLANS

A brief description of the consortium members' individual exploitation plans, as they were presented during the proposal phase follows below. During the project execution and since this is a living document, the members' exploitation plans may be updated accordingly.

9.1.1 NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS (NTUA)

As a public institution of higher education, NTUA is a non-profit organization that will not engage in commercial exploitation of the project's results. However, NTUA can reap significant benefits from the MES-CoBraD project outcomes in numerous ways, as outlined below.

The project team will integrate the MES-CoBraD project's materials and research results into related courses within the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, focusing on the use of Real-World Data, Artificial Intelligence, and data analytics for Complex Brain Disorders. They will conduct seminars and offer further training for undergraduate students as part of their final year projects, encouraging them to explore the project's innovative approaches to diagnosis and treatment.

Postgraduate students enrolled in the MSc in Techno-economic studies will also benefit from the integration of the MES-CoBraD project's results into courses, projects, and seminars, emphasizing the interdisciplinary nature of the project and the importance of collaboration between medical research, data science, and technology.

Moreover, the project's outcomes will serve as a foundation for PhD theses, either directly or indirectly connected to NTUA's scientific contributions to the MES-CoBraD project. Existing team members and new PhD candidates will leverage the project's results in their research, focusing on areas such as data analytics, visualizations, Big Data analytics, and Artificial Intelligence applied to Complex Brain Disorders.

This expertise will enable the NTUA team to publish research papers, present their work at conferences, and participate in other research projects related to the MES-CoBraD project. By doing so, the Decision Support Systems Laboratory will extend its proficiency in these areas, fostering the continued growth and development of the institution's research capabilities while making a positive impact on the lives of those affected by Complex Brain Disorders.

9.1.2 NEUROLOGICAL INSTITUTE OF ATHENS (NIA)

The Neurological Institute of Athens will benefit through the MES- CoBraD Project since its goals are in line with the NIA mission of promoting brain health in Greece and worldwide. More specifically, clinically, the development of easy to administer and expert-based innovative multidisciplinary protocols through MES-CoBraD will help achieve precision diagnostics and for people with CoBraD and their caregivers presenting at the NIA. In addition, the key concept of integrating novel technologies on RWD acquisition and analysis will significantly improve clinical assessment duration and minimise administrative processes, allowing NIA staff to focus on clinical activities and direct care to patients, while also minimising mistakes by improving data acquisition. Moreover, scientifically, the publication of novel research results will help promote the field of Neurology, and medicine in general, in understanding CoBraD, and will further establish the Sleep & Memory Centre and the Epilepsy Centre at the NIA as Centres of Excellence in Europe and internationally. Furthermore, educationally, the new information from the MES-CoBraD will be integrated into the NIA fellowship programs, providing both the best evidence in caring for patients with complex chronic conditions, and a first-hand experience in

participating in multidisciplinary, multinational research projects that will be an asset in their future careers. Finally, this information will also be disseminated directly to educate the NIA patients and public within our regular outreach activities in the community.

9.1.3 FUNDACIÓ PRIVADA INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'HOSPITAL DE LA SANTA CREU I SANT PAU (SP)

IR-HSCSP expects to benefit from the project in multiple dimensions, including: The SP will benefit of the MES-CoBraD project because its alignment with its goals to promoting care for the aging population in Spain and Europe. First, the systematic evaluation of comorbidities in CoBraD will significantly improve clinical care in people with cognitive complaints and cognitive impairment. It will enable the identification of many subjects with co-occurring epilepsy and sleep disorders. Moreover, the implementation of the novel tools developed in this proposal will maximise the information to be gained from RWD data. It has the potential to save times and procedures or serve in decision trees that maximise efficiency of clinical resources in over-stretched memory clinics. Moreover, CoBraD will help us integrate our clinical and research efforts with the epilepsy and sleep units. The role of these comorbidities both as contributing factors to the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative disorders, but also as consequences are two of the hottest scientific topics in the field. Finally, CoBraD will also enable us to generate a European-wide cohort of patients.

9.1.4 VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL (VUB-LSTS)

The motivation of VUB-LSTS for the participation in the project is the intrinsic interest to promote privacy, data protection and security in the emerging innovative solutions and the keenness to identify and facilitate the mitigation of data protection threats and risks. Apart from the unique opportunity to enhance and adapt the EU data protection legal framework, VUB-LSTS will not only monitor legal compliance with the European legal framework but also will contribute to Privacy- and Security-by-Design solutions and upgrade its expertise.

9.1.5 UPPSALA UNIVERSITY (UU)

UU expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project in multiple dimensions. First, adding value to ongoing research that relate to the field of neuroscience and neurology. This may evolve into collaborations with other related European research initiatives and form bi-directional information exchange. Moreover, disseminating results and final knowledge gained from the MES- CoBraD, to academic partners, students, and the public. This may lead to further innovation and other research projects, as well as educational elements such as post-graduate/graduate seminars and courses. Finally, encouraging future or present university students to engage in research related to the ideas proposed in the project.

9.1.6 CLALIT HEALTH SERVICES- RABIN MEDICAL CENTER (CHS-RMC)

The

The CHS-RMC team has leveraged the actions proposed above in multiple dimensions during the brief time of the project.

1. Development of new research infrastructure recruitment of dedicated research personnel: two research coordinator, four neuropsychologists, two neurology residents, two technicians. Purchasing and leasing equipment: centrifuge, actigraphy devices, computer software.

Setting up and testing Research pipelines , translation of forms, data entry methods, MRI acquisition methods, EEG and sleep labs, plasma procuring processing and storage. Moreover, it includes frequent engagement with ethics board and hospital administration, actions enable a sustainable research program into COBRAD after completing the current project.

2. Pilot data collection increases the public's access to expert care by providing more dedicated time for research level clinical evaluations, it increases public engagement in research, trust and rapport in the consortium as a whole. In addition, it increased expertise required for non-research clinical work.
 - a. The CHS-RMC team has begun to establish international research partnerships with leading institutions in Europe and brainstorm new concepts in dementia, epilepsy and sleep neuroscience for the advancement of public health. This will enable the platform to reach new users beyond the consortium, demonstrate its utility for research, assess need of additional COBRAD types for a platform, and suggest new user stories. Titles of the grants and projects applied are listed below : Funded grants since MES-COBRAD inception:
 - i. Assessment of social health determinants impact on neurodegeneration in diverse Israeli populations.
 - ii. Development of Hebrew language models in primary progressive aphasia
 - iii. Genetics of Alzheimer Disease in Jewish and Arab Populations
 - b. Pending grants for CHS-RMC
 - i. Immune phenotyping of genetic frontotemporal dementias
 - ii. Impact of cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease on the safety and efficacy of acute stroke interventions.

9.1.7 KING'S COLLEGE LONDON (KCL)

King's College London expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project in multiple dimensions. More specifically, accumulating and diffusing the knowledge that emerges from the project to be further used for educational purposes (seminars, post/undergraduate courses, etc.) and for exchanging ideas with the academic community. In addition, implement of acquired knowledge in designing more efficient, cost-effective and accurate diagnostic protocols for assessment of people with chronic brain disorders.

9.1.8 HOLISTIC

Holistic comes from a team of executives who have a long and extensive experience in the development of projects in these fields. They have the necessary expertise to undertake and execute complex projects of public, municipal, and private organisations of the EU. Holistic expects not only to enhance added-value provided by participating in the MES-CoBraD project but also to give feedback in the project's methodologies with the academic background in cutting-edge systems and technologies that the team leads. Holistic will provide a wide range of marketing and communication services that will be conducted during and within the project's life, improving its standing in the field. finally, HOLISTIC has at its disposal the required operational infrastructure to conduct the activities foreseen under the MES-CoBraD project proposal in terms of building and office equipment, as well as related software.

9.1.9 SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION (SIMAVI)

Benefiting of 25 years of expertise in the software industry, SIMAVI responds to the market needs in a

dynamic and flexible manner, implementing solutions forecasted by the IT analysts. As the exploitation will be based on the concrete and real demands of the adequate professionals, markets and decision makers, the very innovative approach of the information system is the driving force to guarantee a professional and successful exploitation of the project results. The newly developed solution will strengthen SIMAVI's position on the ICT market and will allow the organisation to approach a new market niche. SIMAVI will exploit the knowledge gained in this R&D project by creating new business opportunities, enhancing SIMAVI software solutions and processes, by leveraging its knowledge to develop niches and specific software applications, which can be derived by the project technologies and methodologies, and contributing to intensive research excellence to Europe's competitive software systems and services.

9.1.10 LIBER

LIBER intends to benefit from the project by connecting project outputs to our network of over 450 research libraries from around Europe. Through involvement in the project, there will be numerous opportunities for engagement and knowledge sharing on data science, research data management, citizen science, and open publishing - areas vital to both the research libraries within LIBER's network and the MES-CoBraD project. In addition, LIBER will impact the project by applying its extensive knowledge in these fields. Over the course of the project, LIBER will assist partners with engagement opportunities for stakeholder groups identified within the proposal. This will ensure that varied and meaningful feedback loops are in place, allowing those who will benefit from the projects outputs the chance to be targeted, engaged, and provide their own input.

9.1.11 ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA S.P.A. (ENG)

As a global IT player in the digital transformation sector, ENG aims to deliver innovative solutions and strategic consultancy to several vertical markets. Between the most relevant ones, the Public Administration sector (also including the Healthcare segment) represents around 26% of the company revenue amount according to the 2018 Consolidated Accounts of the Engineering Group.

Through the Open Public Service Innovation laboratory, as R&D group involved in MES-CoBraD, ENG will exploit the MES-CoBraD results mainly to improve its current offerings dedicated to Public Administrations, healthcare providers and citizens. MES-CoBraD project represents for ENG a relevant opportunity: (a) to further consolidate its expertise on the field of digital platform (by extending its asset Digital Enabler) and on the use of advanced data analytics, AI, and Machine Learning technologies in the context of healthcare services, as well as to (b) strengthen its capabilities of providing innovative services and consultancy to its customers in the health domain.

9.1.12 MICHPOULOS I. & CH. G.P. - TRADE NAME: EVOLUTION PROJECTS(EVOL)

The goal of exploitation in MES-CoBraD is to ensure the sustainability of the project's results beyond the project end and to demonstrate how MES-CoBraD has influenced the whole EU. Exploitation includes multiple forms. More specifically, Research & Development, by engaging new projects (EU-funded or sponsored by other sources), based on the experiences gained in the project, education, e.g., courses, at the university level or in continuing education, etc. Furthermore, community-building around the topics of the project, raising awareness for the addressed problems and the proposed solutions. Moreover, knowledge transfer, from academia to industry, by collaboration or via employees. Finally, contributions to Open-Source projects and standardisation, providing public access to the mix-net framework and encouraging its broad adoption in commercial and public systems for interested parties.

9.1.13 UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH (UE)

UE expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project along multiple dimensions, including adding value to other, ongoing research and innovation projects in relevant domains with that of MES-CoBraD domain, as well as diffuse the knowledge that emerges from MES-CoBraD for the assessment, management and treatment of CoBraD to other health professionals, academics, and scientists. In addition, findings may be further used for educational purposes, including engaging MSc and PhD students that may be interested in this or related research. We will also support the dissemination of results drawing on the experience and networks of our academic community and through our linkages to policy audiences.

9.1.14 CYBERETHICS LAB. (CEL)

CEL expects to benefit from the MES-CoBraD project in multiple dimensions. More specifically, in the data protection and privacy framework: CEL will advance its knowledge on the application of the data protection and privacy framework to the democratisation and political participations fields and ICTs that will be reused to enhance its own current offering to public and private companies on GDPR compliance. Also, in ethics and philosophy issues will be identified and introduced in CEL assessment methods to enrich them, producing relevant results of interest to the academic community. All the acquired knowledge will be used to enhance communication and interaction capacity with health operators and patients' communities with the aim of improving CEL offering of services in the management of complex chronic conditions. Furthermore, CEL will take advantage of the work done for the development of the ETHAI model (Ethical Decision-Making Model for AI) in the following way:

- Participating in the development of dedicated standards, in particular in the CEN/CLC/JTC 21 "Artificial Intelligence", devoted to the identification and adoption of international standards on AI, including the ethical aspects.
- Developing a methodology for the conformity assessment of AI medical systems to the requirements of the AI Act.
- Taking advantage of the issues faced within the framework of the MES-CoBraD project, CEL will fine-tune its methodology of assessment of a system as a medical device and of control of its conformity to the medical device regulation.

11 NEXT STEPS / CONCLUSIONS

In the following subsections, the CDE activities scheduled for the next years of the project are presented. In particular, detailed promotional campaigns adapted to all upcoming events and tailor-made to fit the scientific and technical tasks are designed and implemented with the participation of all partners.

11.1 ACTIONS ON CDE ONLINE CHANNELS

11.1.1 WEBSITE

To increase the website's traffic and establish a loyal audience, a news section was created, where articles that will analyze the research initial results, the structure of the MES-CoBraD platform, and its implemented and potential outcomes are constantly posted. Furthermore, these articles include links to appropriate sections of the website, i.e., the Material section, etc. This reduces the bounce rate since visitors are motivated to explore more webpages. It is envisaged that for the upcoming year at least 4 to 6 articles will be published in the MES-CoBraD news section.

11.1.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

In the upcoming period, the promotional campaign in social media will be more intense, so that it will increase both the project's visibility in social media and the traffic to the website since the MES-CoBraD platform will launch. In particular, the campaign will include 1 to 3 posts per week in each social media account. The role of the social media in promoting the upcoming webinars, and workshops and in the stakeholder engagement strategy is also crucial.

11.1.3 ONLINE MEDIA

The presence of MES-CoBraD in online media will be increased in the upcoming period. Specifically, it is envisaged that a total of 5 articles in external online media will be published. This will lead to an increased traffic to the website, as well as optimisation of the website's SEO since there will be more backlinks towards the website. These articles will include topics regarding the MES-CoBraD research and deliverables, as well as the development of the AI Algorithm and the platform launch. Furthermore, representatives of the project will give interviews to well-known media relevant to the project's scope.

11.1.4 PARTNER'S WEBSITE / BLOGS

In the following period, a series of articles are expected to be published on partners' websites and/or blogs. These articles will focus on the project's outcomes and progress, as well as the partner's contribution. The objective of this promotional activity is to increase the project's visibility as well as the website's traffic and SEO. It is intended that at least one article will be included in each partner's website, while ideally a total of 4 articles per partner are desired. The increase of promotional articles in partners' websites and blogs will support the C&D strategy and help achieve our goals.

11.2 UPDATE ON MATERIALS & NEW CONTENT

11.2.1 MATERIALS UPDATE

All of the project's materials will be updated to reflect the current progress and present the solutions and outcomes deriving from the projects scientific and technical achievements. Dedicated materials will be issued to target specific groups of stakeholders based on the needs identified in the exploitation roadmap as well.

11.2.2 INFOGRAPHICS

A team has been assembled between partners' that will design infographics, presenting the main

outcomes and results of the first years of the project in a visual appealing way. These infographics will also serve as a visual demonstration of the platform's key features and capabilities. We expect them to be ready for launch on the following semester and a dedicated social media campaign will be launched in parallel with their release.

11.2.3 VIDEOS

At least 2 videos will be developed on the following months, related to the platform launch, presenting the key features and capabilities. Taking advantage of the platform training videos already developed internally in the consortium is also an option to generate step-by-step video presentations of the most important platform modules. Another possible video to be produced could include interviews of scientific and technical partners who further elaborate on the MES-CoBraD solutions in a Q/A format.

11.3 EVENTS' PARTICIPATION

11.3.1 WORKSHOPS, PUBLIC EVENTS, DEMONSTRATIONS & MATERIAL

During the recent 2nd workshop, was identified the importance of communicating the outcomes of the MES-CoBraD with targeted and specific audiences (clinicians, clinical researchers, patients, caregivers, policymakers, students, etc), via workshops, public events, demonstrations & regarding the material. Towards this notion, the consortium decided, at the recent workshop, to design, develop, produce and disseminate a one-page informatic leaflet (that might be translated at every project's language), targeted to the clinicians, patients, their advocacy groups, and their caregivers, that will exemplify merely the significance of this project, its potential and implemented outcomes and how they could be a substantial part of the platform's progress and results.

11.3.2 CONFERENCES

Entering the last year of the project and with the imminent launch of the platform, partners are urged to participate in scientific conferences where the project's results can be further disseminated. Exploiting the technologies and methodologies developed relies heavily on the scientific community engaging with the MES-CoBraD project.

11.4 EXPLOITATION & BUSINESS-RELATED ACTIONS

11.4.1 MARKET ANALYSIS

The consortium partners recognized the importance of market analysis as a supplementary tool of the business plan during the last workshop. A market analysis will follow, which will aim to identify the needs MES-CoBraD serves to its targeted customers/users (clinicians, medical researchers, AI researchers, pharma and health tech industries, European Union, patients with CoBraD diseases etc), the market trends, gaps and opportunities, and to produce a strategy for positioning the MES-CoBraD toolkit and the MES-CoBraD outcomes in the market.

11.4.2 VALUE PROPOSITIONS – TARGETED BUSINESS MODEL(S)

The consortium will explore the possibility of identifying the possible customer segments, key resources and exploitation channels for each value proposition of MES-CoBraD BM allowing for a more targeted exploitation of the most promising ones.

11.5 C&D&E PLAN AND REPORT UPDATE

The CDE Plan will be further updated in the final report D9.7 "Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities Report and Plan", which will be finalised in March 2024.

